

**FACULTY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF CROP AND SOIL SCIENCES**

**GENETIC ANALYSIS AND ADAPTABILITY OF SORGHUM
GERMPLASM IN SEMI-ARID ZIMBABWE**

NOKUQALA NYONI

BSc Hon. in Crop Science (Lupane State University)

L0150049A

**A RESEARCH PROJECT PROPOSAL SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL
FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE AWARD OF A
MASTER OF SCIENCE IN CROP SCIENCE DEGREE AT LUPANE
STATE UNIVERSITY**

DECEMBER 2021

DECLARATION

The work presented here is of my own and has not been submitted to any other university for the award of a degree.

Signed: N Nyoni Date: 07/01/22

Nyoni Nokuqala

This research project is submitted with the approval of the academic supervisor.

Signed: Date: 07/01/22

Dr Mcebisi Maphosa

(Department of Crop and Soil Sciences, Lupane State University).

PUBLICATIONS DECLARATION

This thesis is based on the following papers/manuscript:

Nyoni. N, Dube. M, Bhebhe. S, Sibanda. B, Maphosa. M and Bombom. A (2020). Understanding biodiversity in sorghums to support the development of high value bio-based products in sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Cereals and Oilseeds* 11(2): 37-43. DOI: 10.5897/JCO2020.0217

Nyoni. N., Bombom A and Maphosa M. Genetic analysis and adaptability of sorghum germplasm in semi-arid Zimbabwe. To be submitted.

DEDICATION

I would like to dedicate this research work to my late grandfather, Chinai Moyo. He encouraged me to do these studies, but never lived to see my work. To the contribution of my whole family that made me to become who I am today, with honour, I also dedicate this work to them.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor Dr. M. Maphosa for his unreserved professional guidance and supervision throughout the duration of this study. I am grateful for the genetic resources and financial support of the Benefit-Sharing Fund of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (Reference Number LoA/TF/PR-316-Uganda/2019/CBDT) led by Dr Alexander Bombom. Also, I am very grateful to the collaboration and support of the staff in the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Lupane State University for their help, encouragement, advice and generosity to make the study a success. I am also sincerely grateful to my colleagues, classmates and friends Sakhile Ndlovu, Mandlenkosi Dube, Sizo Moyo and Sandiso Bhebhe for their support and encouragement . I extend my gratitude to International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT) members specifically Mthulisi Maya and Farai Dube for their assistance in germplasm acquisition, data collection and data analysis. Finally, I would like to express my deep gratitude to all my family members for their honest support. May the Almighty richly bless you.

Table of Contents	
DECLARATION	i
PUBLICATIONS DECLARATION	ii
DEDICATION	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iv
LIST OF TABLES	ix
LIST OF FIGURES	x
LIST OF APPENDICES	xi
ABSTRACT	xii
CHAPTER ONE	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Agriculture in Zimbabwe	1
1.2 Sorghum production and its importance	2
1.3 Diversity of sorghum.....	2
1.4 Importance of genetic diversity in sorghum.....	4
1.5 Statement of the problem	5
1.6 Justification of the study	6
1.7 Main objective.....	6
1.8 Specific objectives.....	6
CHAPTER TWO	8
LITERATURE REVIEW	8
2.1 Agriculture and climate change.....	8
2.2 Biodiversity of sorghum.....	9
2.3 Sorghum germplasm	10
2.4 Chemical composition of sorghum	11
2.5 Common and prospective uses of sorghum.....	12
2.6 Adaptation mechanisms of sorghum to drought	13
2.7 Sorghum production requirements	15
2.7.1 Temperature requirements	15

2.7.2 Water requirements.....	15
2.7.3 Day length.....	15
2.8 Sorghum production statistics in Zimbabwe.....	16
2.9 Constraints to sorghum production in Zimbabwe.....	17
2.9.1 Biotic constraints	17
2.9.2 Abiotic constraints.....	18
2.9.3 Socio-economic constraints.....	19
2.10 Breeding of sorghum.....	21
2.10.1 Importance of genetic diversity in sorghum breeding.....	22
2.10.2 Breeding for heat tolerance.....	22
2.10.3 Breeding for drought tolerance.....	23
2.10.4 Breeding for cold tolerance	23
2.10.5 Breeding for water logging tolerance	24
2.10.6 Breeding for improved grain quality	24
2.11 Analysis of genetic diversity	26
2.11.1 Analysis of genetic parameter	26
2.11.2 Multivariate methods for genetic diversity analysis.....	27
2.12 Genotype main effects and Genotype by Environment Interaction (GGE) biplot analysis	27
2.13 Sectional conclusion.....	28
CHAPTER THREE	30
GENETIC VARIABILITY OF SELECTED SORGHUM GENOTYPES BASED	30
ON QUANTITATIVE TRAITS	30
3.1 Introduction.....	30
3.2 Materials and Methods.....	30
3.2.1 Experimental site	30
3.2.2 Experimental materials, design and procedures	31
3.2.3 Measurements and data collection.....	33
3.2.4 Data Analyses	34
3.3 Results	34
3.3.1 Analysis of variance for quantitative traits in 49 sorghum genotypes	34
3.3.2 Cluster Analysis.....	36

3.4 Discussion	40
3.4.1 Analysis of variance for 14 quantitative traits in selected sorghum genotypes.....	40
3.4.2 Cluster Analysis using 13 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes.....	41
CHAPTER FOUR.....	42
ESTIMATION OF GENETIC PARAMETERS AND EXPECTED GENETIC ADVANCE IN ASSEMBLED SORGHUM GERMPLASM.....	42
4.1 Introduction	42
4.2 Materials and Methods	42
4.2.4 Genetic parameters analysis	43
4.3 Results	44
4.4 Discussion	45
4.4.1 Genetic parameters for 9 quantitative traits.....	45
CHAPTER FIVE	48
TRAIT ASSOCIATION ANALYSIS IN SELECTED SORGHUM GENOTYPES.....	48
5.1 Introduction	48
5.2 Materials and Methods	49
5.2.4 Statistical Analyses.....	49
5. 3 Results	50
5.3.1 Correlation analyses	50
5. 3.2 Path coefficient analysis for grain yield	50
5. 3.3 Principal component analysis	53
5. 4 Discussion	56
5.4.1 Correlation analysis	56
5.4.2 Path coefficient analysis	56
5.4.3 Principal component analysis (PCA).....	57
CHAPTER SIX.....	59
GENOTYPE MAIN EFFECTS PLUS GENOTYPE BY ENVIRONMENT INTERACTION FOR GRAIN YIELD IN SELECTED SORGHUM GENOTYPES ACROSS THREE ENVIRONMENTS	59
6.1 Introduction	59
6. 2 Materials and Methods.....	60
6. 2.1 Experimental sites.....	60
6. 2.2 Experimental materials, design and procedures	61

6.2.3 Data Analyses	61
6.3 Results	62
6.3.1 Analysis of variance for grain yield	62
6.3.2 Genotype evaluation by AMMI biplot	63
6.3.3 Comparison of environments based on the concentric circle	65
6.3.5 Environment evaluation by GGE biplot	68
6.4 Discussion	69
6.4.1 Genotype main effects plus genotype by environment interaction for grain yield in selected sorghum genotypes across three environments	69
CHAPTER SEVEN	72
CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PESPECTIVES	72
REFERENCES	74
APPENDICES	95
Appendix 1 : ANOVA table for AMMI model.....	95
Appendix 2: Environment means and scores	95
Appendix 3: Environment means and variances	95
Appendix 4: AMMI-estimates per environment	96
Appendix 5: Table of first four AMMI selections per environment	99
Appendix 6:Agglomerative cluster analysis tables	99

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Comparative analysis of nutrient composition of sorghum versus other staple cereals.....	12
Table 2: Sorghum genotypes, their identity, type and source used in the 2020/2021 evaluation season.....	31
Table 3: Analysis of variance for 14 quantitative traits in selected sorghum genotypes.....	36
Table 4: Cluster membership of 49 sorghum genotypes derived from the Agglomerative method of hierarchical clustering.....	37
Table 5: Comparison of quantitative traits of the four clusters of 49 sorghum genotypes derived from agglomerative clustering method.....	39
Table 6: Genetic parameters for 9 quantitative traits of selected sorghum genotypes.....	44
Table 7: Correlation analysis of 14 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes.....	51
Table 8: Path coefficient analysis showing direct (bold) and indirect effects of 12 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes on sorghum grain yield.....	52
Table 9: Principal components indicating standard deviation, proportion of variance and Eigen values.....	53
Table 10: Description of sites used to evaluate G×E effects on sorghum grain yield.....	61
Table 11: AMMI analysis of variance for sorghum grain yield (Kg ha ⁻¹) of 49 sorghum genotypes evaluated across three locations of Zimbabwe.....	63
Table 12: Table of first four AMMI selections per environment.....	65

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Sorghum production statistics from 1961-2019.....	17
Figure 2: Clustering of 49 sorghum genotypes into 4 cluster using the Agglomerative method of hierarchical clustering.....	38
Figure 3: Biplot analysis of 13 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes(arranged by their plot number) evaluated.....	55
Figure 4: AMMI biplot (PC1 vs PC2) for sorghum yield with 49 genotypes and 3 environments..	64
Figure 5: The Average Environment coordination (AEC) view of the GGE biplot ranking genotypes (replicated two times) and environments relative to the center of the concentric circles.....	66
Figure 6: A 'which-won-where' GGE biplot based on a genotype by environment grain yield data of the 49 sorghum genotypes and evaluated in three environments.....	67
Figure 7: Discriminativeness vs Representativeness" GGE biplot for the 3 environments in the study.....	69

LIST OF APPENDICES

Appendix 1: ANOVA table for AMMI model.....	94
Appendix 2: Environment means and scores.....	94
Appendix 3: Environment means and variance.....	94
Appendix 4: AMMI estimates per environment.....	95
Appendix 5: Table of first four AMMI selections per environment.....	98
Appendix 6: Agglomerative cluster analysis tables.....	98

ABSTRACT

Sorghum is the second most important grain cereal after maize in most African countries, including Zimbabwe. Despite its importance, sorghum productivity is still very low due to a number of biotic, abiotic and socio-economic constraints and use of adapted genotypes could double current yields. Sorghum has a wide genetic diversity and to date there are some sorghum landraces and local species still grown by farmers in Zimbabwe whose genetic diversity has not been established.

The broad objective of the study was to enhance full utilization of sorghum germplasm collections in breeding programmes and thus strengthen sorghum production and productivity in marginal areas of Zimbabwe. The specific objectives were to; (i) assess genetic variability of selected sorghum genotypes based on quantitative traits, (ii) estimate genetic parameters and expected genetic advance in assembled sorghum germplasm, (iii) evaluate trait association in selected sorghum genotypes and also (iv) to assess the effect of the genotype and environment (G×E) in sorghum grain yield in multi-environmental trials. Forty-nine genotypes were evaluated in the present study. Assessment of genetic variability of the selected sorghum genotypes based on quantitative traits, estimation of genetic parameters and expected genetic advance and evaluation of trait association in selected the sorghum genotypes were all done at Lupane State University Farm during the 2020/21 cropping season. Data were collected on 14 quantitative traits which were; days to 50% flowering, days to physiological maturity, plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf length, leaf width, stem diameter, plant count (number of plants per plot), number of productive tillers, number of non-productive tillers, exertion length, panicle length (head size), panicle weight (head weight) and grain yield per plot. Analysis of variance showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for some the traits studied among the 49 genotypes. The studied genotypes exhibited genetic diversity as they were grouped into four clusters. There was a high broad sense

heritability ($H^2 > 60\%$) for days to physiological maturity, plant height, number of leaves, leaf length, exertion and head size. The expected genetic advance expressed as a percentage of means for the traits ranged from 13.57% for leaf width and 150.99 % for exertion. Pearson's phenotypic correlation analysis and principal component analysis was performed to determine the association among the studied traits. There was a strong positive correlation between grain yield and head weight ($r^2 = 0.87$). In the present study path coefficient analysis for grain yield revealed that head weight had the highest positive direct effect on grain yield whilst days to physiological maturity had the highest negative direct effect on grain yield. Lupane State University farm, Matopo Research Station and Gwebi Variety Testing Centre were the 3 sites used to assess the effect of the genotype and environment ($G \times E$) in sorghum grain yield. Analyses were done using Additive Main Effects and Multiplicative Interactions (AMMI) and the Genotype plus Genotype by Environment (GGE) analysis method. The AMMI analysis revealed that the trial environments and the genotypes were diverse ($P < 0.05$). The genotype and genotype-environment interaction (GGE biplot) analyses identified genotypes with wide adaptation as well as genotypes with specific adaptation. Genotypes which were widely adapted to three test environments were G44 (IS 10214), G17 (NGB 1862), G15 (NGB 1260), G50 (Macia), G49 (IS 30047), G48 (IS 9381), G12 (NGB 1695), G9 (NGB 3084), G52 (SV 4), G32 (SS 2020), G1 (NGB 1260), G26 (IS 29925), G5 (NGB 3105), G3 (NGB 3133), G37 (IS 24272), G38 (IS 37158), G19 (NGB 3092), G40 (IS 23901), G7 (NGB 1698), G20 (NGB 3124), G29 (IS 13996), G31 (IS 2419), G35 (IS 29925), G51 (SV 2), G2 (NGB 3093), G8 (NGB 1156), G30 (IS 23908), G18 (NGB 3283). Genotype G26 (IS 29925) was specifically adapted to Lupane, genotypes G40 (IS 23901) was adapted to Gwebi while genotypes G29 (IS 13996) and G20 (NGB 3124) were specifically adapted to Matopo. The present study revealed that Matopo was the most ideal environment for sorghum evaluation.

It is recommended that when breeding for sorghum grain yield it is important to select genotypes which have high head weight, longer heads (panicles) be selected since they are correlated to grain yield. Additionally, selection of multiple traits simultaneously using trait association results in a realistic response to selection for all the traits that are being combined. This can speed up breeding for the traits instead of focusing on one trait at a time.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Agriculture in Zimbabwe

Today's agriculture is characterised by the use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, extensive irrigation, large scale animal husbandry and reliance of machinery in order to improve productivity especially in the developed world. Agriculture continues to occupy an important position in the global economy. It still remains as the key sector that contributes significantly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment and foreign exchange earnings in the economy of many countries. In Zimbabwe, agriculture occupies a central place in the economy and contributes about 15-18% GDP with over 40% of national export earnings and 60% of raw materials to agro-industries. Over 70% of the population derives its livelihoods from the agricultural sector (Comprehensive Agricultural Policy Framework, 2012). The diverse climatic and edaphic conditions allow for a large variety of food and cash crops to be produced in Zimbabwe. The major food crops include maize, sorghum, pearl millet, finger millet, ground nuts, wheat, cow peas, bambara nuts and sweet potatoes. The major commercial crops which generate cash income are seen as men's crops, and these include tobacco, cut-flowers, sugar cane, cotton, chilled vegetables, coffee, fruits and tea. The significant part of the crops that are produced commercially, are being exported to other countries. Conversely, most of the crops that are produced in the communal area are for consumption. Observed climate change is already affecting agricultural productivity in Zimbabwe through increasing temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and greater frequency of some extreme events such as drought and flooding. Water resources for food production have been affected through changing rates of precipitation and evaporation, ground water levels, and dissolved oxygen content (Huntington et al., 2017). Under this situation, there is a great necessity

of multidisciplinary research to breed for high yielding varieties which are adapted and tolerant to abiotic and biotic stresses and sustain crop productivity.

1.2 Sorghum production and its importance

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor L*) is a grain crop grown worldwide for human consumption. It is a dietary staple for millions of people living in over 30 countries in the subtropical and semi-arid regions of Africa and Asia. In Africa sorghum is ranked second after maize (Mofokeng et al., 2017). Currently, the largest sorghum producers are the USA, India, Nigeria and Mexico (FAOSTAT, 2017). Although sorghum is very rich in energy and non-energy nutrients, it is generally regarded as a poor man's crop produced with no value addition by the poorest people (Ramatoulaye et al., 2016). It is consumed as whole grain or processed into flour, from which traditional meals are prepared. It also serves as an important source of cattle feed and fodder. Sorghum is also used in industries such as the animal feed sector, alcohol distilleries, and starch industries. In the United States, Australia and other developed countries, sorghum is mainly grown for animal feed. Sorghum grows comparatively faster and also gives good yields of grains with very large quantities of fodder. Since, sorghum has high starch content of around 60 - 77%, it is used in production of bio-industrial products like bioethanol, glucose and it also serves as source material for isolation of starch (Shewale and Aniruddha, 2011). Malting and brewing industries also use sorghum for the production of lager and stout.

1.3 Diversity of sorghum

Sorghum is a unique C₄ photosynthetic crop that adapts to drought, high temperatures; water logging, saline and infertile soils (Verma et al., 2017). It is therefore cultivated in dry and warm climates where other cereal crops cannot thrive. Sorghum germplasm is classified into wild and cultivated races and shows great variability in genotypes and phenotypes. There are mainly five

types of sorghum which are; grain sorghum, forage sorghum, sweet sorghum, biomass sorghum and broom sorghum (Buschmann, 2018). There are some under-utilized special types of sorghum (usually referred to as specialty sorghums) such as waxy, heterowaxy and tannin hybrids which offer benefits for nutrition and or production of novel products (Gonzalez, 2005). Novel products such as pet foods, poultry rations and gluten free foods have been produced from these specialty sorghums and some of these specialty sorghums have high antioxidant levels which are beneficial to human health (Turner, 2004). In recent years, sweet sorghum is now of great interest. It is a type of sorghum that grows rapidly and has a higher biomass production as compared to grain sorghum. Exploring the renewable energy from different sources is the focus of current research, as the present energy resources fossil fuels, are rapidly declining. Studies have revealed that sweet sorghum is a promising energy crop that can be cultivated worldwide under diverse agro-climatic conditions with a requirement for a relatively less nitrogen fertilizer and water when compared to sugarcane and maize. Compared to other types, the sugar syrup from sweet sorghum gives per unit area the highest yield of biomass suitable for processing it into sugar as well as into solid and liquid fuels (Pabendon et al., 2017). In Zimbabwe less is known about sweet sorghum and it is an under-utilized crop which can be extensively cultivated to produce food grain for humans and livestock, produce fodder and also other value-added products like ethanol and syrups (Makabane, 2015).

Sorghum has one of the largest crop germplasm collections, consisting of more than 42,000 accessions worldwide (Tesfaye, 2017). It is this diversity that is exploited so as to improve the crop in terms of its environmental adaptability and acquiring better agronomic traits from the crop species. For any given country, it is important to identify and select the best performing varieties and genotypes that satisfy the local food and industrial demands. Knowledge of genetic diversity of a crop helps breeders in choosing desirable parents for the breeding program and gene

introgression from distantly related germplasm. The more diverse genotypes or accessions can be crossed to produce superior hybrids with resistance to abiotic and biotic stresses. Understanding the wealth of genetic diversity in sorghum will facilitate further improvement of this crop for its genetic architecture. Crops can be genetically enhanced through conventional breeding if there is genetic variation and the desirable traits are heritable (Tesfaye, 2017).

1.4 Importance of genetic diversity in sorghum

Genetic diversity is the amount of different inherited traits among individuals of a variety or population of a species, in this case crop species. Conservation of crop genetic diversity is essential for present and future human well-being. Knowledge of genetic diversity of crops helps breeders to select desirable parents for breeding programs and gene introgression from distantly related germplasm (Rao and Hodgkin, 2002). More diverse genotypes or accessions can be crossed to produce superior hybrids with better performance and adaptability. Morphological traits are the most common traits used to analyze genetic diversity. They do not require complicated equipment and methodology. These simple, observable and measurable (quantitative) morphological traits are the useful tools for primary genetic diversity study as they provide a quick and useful approach for assessing the range of diversity in the crop species (Sinha and Kumaravadivel, 2016). The morphological characteristics used in characterization are usually related to the plant structure, stem, leaf and fruit. Morphological traits have been used in several studies to estimate genetic variability of cultivated sorghum (Shehzad *et al.*, 2009 and Aduyna, 2014). This genetic variability of cultivated sorghum varieties and their wild relatives (available as germplasm) mutually form an unlimited source of breeding material for the development of improved varieties (Sinha and Kumaravadivel, 2016). Genetic diversity of sorghum occurs naturally and arises due to

geographical separation or due to genetic barriers to crossability. In order to analyze this genetic diversity, effective evaluation of sorghum genotypes is required (Mofokeng et al., 2017).

1.5 Statement of the problem

Despite its vast genetic diversity and having one of the largest germplasm collections in the world, sorghum has been generally neglected by main stream research. It still remains as one of the under-utilized crop that could play a key role in hunger alleviation and economic development programs especially in Zimbabwe (Chakauya et al., 2006). This potentially promising crop has had lower production levels compared to other cereals. This is because sorghum lacks status, that is, the crop is considered as a coarse grain fit for animal feed or food for the poor populations thus it is termed “the poor man’s crop”. It is also regarded as a crop of low value because of the tannins that are present at seed coats of some sorghum grains, large proportion of prolamine a protein which cannot be easily digested by humans and limited product portfolio. In Zimbabwe sorghum is mainly grown by small scale and communal farmers in the semi-arid parts of the country. In these areas, sorghum is usually grown and maintained using traditional practices and cultural preferences with limited inputs in conditions of sparse rainfall, low soil fertility, and face a range of disease and pest problems leading to low yields (Chakauya et al., 2006). There are sorghum landraces still grown by farmers in semi-arid Zimbabwe and other local species available which have not been studied and their genetic diversity has not been established. This natural genetic diversity is endangered by destruction of habitats and rapid adoption of modern agricultural practices (Mujaju and Chakauya et al., 2008). Understanding the genetic diversity of sorghum germplasm from different parts of Zimbabwe could help identify the different genotypes which are more adaptable and can be used to produce value added products, which will in turn help to improve sorghum production in the region and in the country.

1.6 Justification of the study

Sorghum is a very diverse crop that can easily adapt to drought prone and marginal environments. Studying the genetic diversity of sorghum germplasm collections from Zimbabwe and other areas attracts special interest because a large amount of genetic variation is present in cultivated and wild sorghum germplasm in Zimbabwe and this diversity has not been fully investigated. Over the years studies have dealt with evaluating the diversity in sorghum based solely on morphological traits using smaller collections of exotic grain material. Although these provide useful information about the genetic variability among accessions, the genotype of some available sorghum germplasm still remains unknown. It has therefore been reported that using quantitative morphological traits using bigger collection of both exotic and indigenous germplasm could be more effective in evaluating the genetic diversity of accessions. However, a few studies have assessed sorghum's genetic diversity using morphological traits under Zimbabwean conditions. Hence the present study sought to determine the extent of diversity among forty-nine sorghum genotypes/accessions and evaluate their adaptability to some semi-arid parts of Zimbabwe using quantitative traits and identify sorghum accessions that are superior in desirable characteristics.

1.7 Main objective

To enhance full utilization of sorghum germplasm collections in breeding programmes and thus strengthen sorghum production and productivity in marginal areas of Zimbabwe.

1.8 Specific objectives

- To assess genetic variability of selected sorghum genotypes based on quantitative traits
- To estimate genetic parameters and expected genetic advance in assembled sorghum germplasm

- To evaluate trait association in selected sorghum genotypes
- To assess the effect of the genotype and environment (G×E) in sorghum grain yield in multi-environmental trials

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Agriculture and climate change

Increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) has led to the enhanced greenhouse effect and has resulted in global warming and climate change (Lenke *et al.*, 2015). Indications of climate change are; increased temperatures, melting glaciers, extreme weather events and shifting seasons (Lenke *et al.*, 2015). Climate changes' effect on agricultural production is of utmost concern as agriculture is the primary source of food and therefore is critical for human survival. The accelerating rate of climate change conjoined with increased global population threaten world food security (OECD, 2016). High temperatures reduce yields of the most important crops and encourage weed, pest and disease proliferation. Changes in precipitation patterns increase the chances of crop failure and production declines.

Climate change is one of the most profound threats to small holder agriculture in the semi-arid and arid regions as farmers in these regions rely on rainfed agriculture, have limited access to capital and technology and face many other production constraints (Nciizah *et al.*, 2021). As a result, if the changing climatic condition continue unabated, rainfed agricultural systems will become unsustainable with severe food and nutritional security implications. There is therefore need to adopt adaptation and mitigation strategies that will ensure resilience to climate change. These adaptation measures may have the potential to reduce the adverse impacts of climate change (Nciizah *et al.*, 2021). Several adaptation and mitigation strategies have been proposed and these include use of drought tolerant, short season varieties, adjustment of planting dates, erosion control and soil protection (IPCC, 2007).

Maize as a staple for most countries in Southern Africa is susceptible to drought, the high temperatures and erratic rainfall have resulted in low yields of this staple crop. There is urgent need to focus on alternative crops that can do well under the current climatic conditions and are relevant to farmers in the semi-arid areas. Small grain crops have been shown to thrive well under unfavorable conditions and these should be adopted especially in areas facing challenges due to climate change. Accordingly, sorghum is expected to play an important role in meeting the world's food demand in the face of climate change, land degradation and increasing water scarcity.

2.2 Biodiversity of sorghum

Sorghum belongs to the genus *Sorghum*, tribe Andropogoneae, Poaceae family which is made up three main species namely *S. bicolor*, *S. halepense* and *S. propinquum* (Kunth) Hitchc. (Verma *et al.*, 2017). *Sorghum bicolor* includes all the cultivated sorghums and is classified into five races which are; Bicolor, Kafir, Durra, Caudatum and Guinea. The Bicolor race is characterized by a loose panicle with large glumes covering the grain and is found in Asia and Africa. The Kafir is characterized by a cylindrical and compact head made of symmetrical flattened grain and is mostly grown in Southern and Eastern Africa. Durra sorghums have a very compact panicle with a curved peduncle, they are mostly found in but not only confined to East Africa, India, and the Middle East. Caudatum sorghums have asymmetric grain flattened on the ventral surface and has varying panicle shapes. This race is grown in Central and East Africa. The Guinea race is very tall and has a loose panicle and spikelets with open glumes covering elliptical grain and is found in West Africa (Harla and De Wet, 1972; Buschmann, 2018). The center of origin of cultivated sorghum is Ethiopia, from where it was disseminated to other regions of the world (Tesfaye, 2017). Cultivated sorghum is a genetically diverse diploid ($2n = 20$). It is sexually compatible with some of its wild or weedy relatives such as Johnson grass (*Sorghum halepense*) (OECD, 2017). Wide

sorghum biodiversity has been reported within and among cultivars at morphological and genotypic level. Plant breeders exploit this biodiversity for crop improvement that meets specific requirements crucial for food and nutrition security and livelihoods (Tesfaye, 2017). Crop biodiversity present in sorghum provides the opportunity for development of specialty sorghum types targeting niche markets and end uses.

2.3 Sorghum germplasm

Sorghum germplasm is unique not only in size but in diversity. India has enormous diversity of sorghum in both cultivated and wild species; about 19 402 and 36 774 accessions of sorghum are being maintained at the National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (NBPGR), New Delhi and the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT) (Chavan *et al.*, 2018). Ethiopia has 6 000 sorghum accessions at its national genebank. Important traits reported from Ethiopian sorghum include cold tolerance, drought resistance, resistance to sorghum shoot fly, disease and pest resistance, grain quality and resistance to grain mold, high sugar content in the stalks, and high lysine and protein (Gedifew and Tsige, 2019). Globally close to 250 000 sorghum germplasm accessions have been collected and conserved in genebanks, of which (ICRISAT), India and the Plant Genetic Resources Conservation Unit, Southern Regional Plant Introduction Station, University of Georgia and USA-ADR all conserve about 32 % of the total global sorghum collections (Wang *et al.*, 2016). Germplasm diversity representative subsets such as core and mini core collections and genotyping based reference set have been established in sorghum providing access to large diversity. The sorghum mini core collection established at the ICRISAT is being widely used for identification of sources for the resistance to various biotic and abiotic stresses and for agronomic and grain nutritional traits. Large genetic and genomic resources are available in sorghum and the re-sequencing of diverse germplasm resources

including the mini core collection and wild and weedy relatives will provide researchers opportunities to relate sequence variations with phenotypic traits of interest and their utilization in sorghum improvement (Upadhyaya *et al.*, 2016). Sorghum is threatened by rapid adoption of highly improved crop varieties many of which are introductions and poorly adapted. Together with genetic resources, indigenous knowledge associated with the cultivation, utilization and conservation is also endangered. Unless something is done to conserve and re-popularize their use, this natural resource may be lost forever (Muui, 2014).

2.4 Chemical composition of sorghum

The nutrient composition of sorghum is comparable to that of other cereals (Table 1) making it a suitable crop choice to complement dietary and energy needs for populations in areas where other cereals are not well adapted. Sorghum contains approximately 4.4 to 21.1% protein, 55 to 75% starch, 0.5 to 7.6% lipids, 0.7 to 4.2% soluble sugars and 1 to 6% crude fiber on a dry weight basis. Approximately 80, 16 and 3% of the protein is contained in the endosperm, embryo, and pericarp, respectively. The endosperm is made up of 80 to 82% starch, which is comprised of 70 to 80% branched amylopectin and 20 to 30% amylose (Ratnavathi and Patil, 2014). The starch for waxy, glutinous sorghum is almost 100% amylopectin with no amylose. Sorghum grain also contains some anti-nutritional factors such as tannins and phytins. These bind to proteins and other nutrients present in grain making them unavailable for the intestinal absorption, thus inhibiting their digestibility (Queiroz *et al.*, 2015).

Table 1. Comparative analysis of nutrient composition of sorghum versus other staple cereals

Cereal type	Protein (g)	Fat (g)	Crude fibre (g)	Carbohydrate (g)	Energy (kcal)	Calcium (mg)	Iron (mg)
Rice (brown)	7.9	2.7	1.0	76.0	363	33	1.8
Wheat	11.6	2.0	2.0	71.0	348	30	3.5
Maize	9.2	4.6	2.8	73.0	358	26	2.7
Sorghum	10.4	3.1	2.0	70.7	329	25	5.4
Pearl millet	11.8	4.8	2.3	67.0	363	42	11.0
Finger millet	7.7	1.5	3.6	72.6	336	35	3.9

Source: Muui 2014

2.5 Common and prospective uses of sorghum

More than 35% of world sorghum production is dedicated to human consumption, while the rest is for animal feed, brewery and other industrial products (Kangama, 2017). Besides the traditional use of sorghum at household level there are several raw materials derived from the crop such as starch, fiber, dextrose syrup, biofuels, edible oils and gluten free feed (Muui, 2014). Furthermore, crop residues provide sources of building materials, and fuel, particularly in the semi -arid tropics (SAT). In Africa, white and red sorghum have been traditionally used to produce opaque low-alcohol beers such as lager and stout on a large industrial scale. The darker sorghums are usually avoided because of high levels of tannins; however, some farmers prefer them because it is

believed that the tannins play a defensive role against fungi, insects and birds (Ramatoulaye *et al.*, 2016).

2.6 Adaptation mechanisms of sorghum to drought

Drought tolerance/resistance is a complex trait and its expression depends on the interaction of different physiological, morphological and biochemical characters. Drought resistance mechanisms include drought tolerance, drought avoidance and survival (Kidanemariam, 2019). A plant is said to be drought tolerant when it is able to withstand moisture deficit, maintains appropriate physiological processes and protect cellular and metabolic integrity of its cells and tissues (Xiong *et al.*, 2006). Drought avoidance is the ability of the plant to reduce water loss from its leaves and efficiently extract water from the soil and thus conserve water (Ludlow and Muchow, 1990). Survival is defined as the ability of the plant to survive drought regardless of its yield (Amelework *et al.*, 2015). Sorghum employs tolerance, avoidance and survival mechanisms and their combinations for its resilience to drought stress (Hadebe *et al.*, 2016). Boyles *et al.* (2019) revealed that sorghum's adaptation to drought is due to its unique crop physiology, phenology and phenotypic plasticity.

Sorghum has a well-developed and extensive root system which can reach up to two metres in the absence of impeding soil layers. This allows the crop to efficiently access water even from a lateral distance of 1.6 metres from the plant. Other roots characteristics include increased number of secondary roots, volume and dry weight (Krupa *et al.*, 2017). Long narrow pointy leaves with smaller leaf area reduce transpiration hence preventing desiccation (Hadebe *et al.*, 2016). Sorghum leaves roll up during hot and dry conditions. Leaf rolling occurs when the leaf water potential is low (Krupa *et al.*, 2017). Thick waxy cuticles on leaves and stem prevent excessive water loss when there is water stress. This enhances water use efficiency (WUE) in sorghum. High yields can

be obtained as compared to other major cereal crops during drought years due to its high WUE (Assefa *et al.*, 2010). Some sorghum genotypes exhibit lower stomatal conductance and this is associated with increased leaf temperature which give rise to high transpiration efficiency. Both the leaf temperature and transpiration are controlled by a cooling system induced by stomatal closure (Verma *et al.*, 2018). High transpiration efficiency (limited transpiration) allows sorghum to conserve soil moisture and increase its availability during grain filling (Chikuwal, 2018). Sorghum's transpiration ratio is 1:310 compared to a ratio of 1:400 for maize (Hadebe *et al.*, 2016).

Some sorghum genotypes exhibit lower leaf senescence, that is, they stay green for a long time. They are able to retain chlorophyll and maintain photosynthesis during grain filling under drought stress conditions. Stay green is a result of developmental regulation which reduces the size of upper leaves and canopy size. This in turn lowers transpiration and so results in lower water demand. These genotypes with this stay green trait produce higher yields under drought stress conditions (Borrell *et al.*, 2014). Osmotic adjustment is another drought adaptation mechanism found in sorghum. Osmotic adjustments are vital for maintaining water content in leaves under water stress. They occur through the accumulation of organic and inorganic solutes, production of antioxidants and stabilization of amino acids and proteins under drought stress (Ndlovu *et al.*, 2021).

Other drought stress tolerance traits in sorghum include maintenance of efficient photosynthesis, improved pollen viability, panicle exertion, improved seed weight and canopy temperature depression (Chiluwal, 2018). Sorghum has a peculiar flowering habit called early morning flowering whereby the plant completes flowering before dawn. This helps to maintain pollen viability during drought stress conditions (Ndlovu *et al.*, 2021). In conclusion it can be said that this special crop adopts quiescence adoptive mechanisms and can remain dormant during drought stress and resume growth once favorable condition are restored (Assefa *et al.*, 2010).

2.7 Sorghum production requirements

Sorghum grows well on low potential shallow soils and can be successfully cultivated on soils with a pH between 5.5 and 8.5 since it is more tolerant to alkaline soils compared to other grain crops. Sorghum can also tolerate shorter periods of water logging. Climatic requirements for sorghum production can be divided into temperature, water needs and day length requirements (Lubadde *et al.*, 2019).

2.7.1 Temperature requirements

Sorghum grows best in warm areas and it requires high temperatures for good germination and growth to take place. Germination does not occur at temperatures below 5°C. For optimum germination to occur, soil temperature must be 15°C or higher at a depth of 5 cm. Growth and development require temperatures of 25 to 30°C. However very high temperatures (35°C) can suspend flower initiation and flower primordia development. Temperatures below freezing point may kill sorghum plants (Seed-co sorghum growers guide, 2019).

2.7.2 Water requirements

Sorghum is grown mostly in areas with an annual rainfall range of 300 to 750 mm. It is grown in areas which are too dry for maize as it is drought tolerant.

2.7.3 Day length

Sorghum is a short-day plant, which means that it requires short days and long nights before it proceeds to the reproductive stage. The optimum photoperiod that induces flower formation, is between 10 and 11 hours. Photoperiods longer than 12 hours stimulate vegetative growth and suspend reproductive development (Lubadde *et al.*, 2019).

2.8 Sorghum production statistics in Zimbabwe

Sorghum production dominates crop mixes in semi-arid and arid areas of Zimbabwe, that is, Matabeleland, Masvingo and Mashonaland East. The production data on sorghum can be considered as only the best estimates that are available, as production data from small subsistence farms are difficult to obtain. It is also likely that grain distribution and consumption throughout the semi-arid regions vary widely among seasons, communities and families. One reason for the lack of information is the fact that to collect this information extensive surveys are needed. Several factors such as cost, time, labor, transportation and accessibility of villages in rural areas have to be considered before a survey is carried out. Available estimates compiled by the world bank show that although the production of sorghum in Zimbabwe fluctuated substantially in recent years, it tended to decrease through 1970 - 2019 period ending at 41,000 tonnes in 2019 (Figure 1) (Musara *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1. Sorghum production statistics from 1961-2019.

Source: World bank 2021

2.9 Constraints to sorghum production in Zimbabwe

The yield gap between the potential yield and the actual yield obtained by farmers in Zimbabwe is still big (Sodziwa, 2015). This is mainly due to a number of factors that may be classified into biotic, abiotic, and socio-economic constraints (Waddington *et al.*, 2010). Among these, the socio-economic constraints in sorghum production play a major role in low productivity, especially in the semi-arid and arid parts of Zimbabwe.

2.9.1 Biotic constraints

The most important biotic constraints that affect sorghum productivity are birds and Striga. Phiri *et al.*, (2019) noted that a major challenge faced by sorghum farmers is the depredation by birds

especially quelea birds. Research has shown that bird scaring increases labour requirements and this makes farmers less keen to produce sorghum. Several studies revealed Striga (Dereje *et al.*, 2016; Ali and Mahdi, 2017) as an important sorghum pest. Striga can be controlled by proper field management and adoption of resistant cultivars (Ejeta, 2007).

Other important biotic constraints that affect grain yield in sorghum are diseases; namely ergot disease (*Claviceps africana*), rusts (*Puccinia purpurea*) and anthracnose (*Collectotrichum graminicola*) (Bhanderi *et al.*, 2015 and Silva *et al.*, 2015). The diseases which include grain mould and ergot reduce the economic value of the grain as they produce toxic chemicals which affect grain quality (Mulima, 2017). Biological and chemical control methods can be used, but these are not readily available or affordable to poor resourced farmers. Disease control can also be achieved through use of resistant germplasm and crop residue management by cleaning the fields after harvesting. Therefore, identification and selection of genotypes with greater levels of disease resistance could be more sustainable and effective for grain yield increase in the smallholder farming sector (White *et al.*, 2012).

2.9.2 Abiotic constraints

Sorghum is naturally adapted to variable climatic and soil conditions. The crop can tolerate drought and high-temperatures better than many crops (Olembo *et al.*, 2010). However, Gill *et al.* (2001) reported that heat and drought are factors that significantly contribute to yield reduction and the water deficit affects plant growth, metabolism and productivity. Other abiotic constraints affecting sorghum plants are salinity, cold stress and osmotic pressure (Gill *et al.*, 2003).

2.9.3 Socio-economic constraints

The major sorghum socio-economic constraints in Zimbabwe are markets, high seed prices, limited access to markets for inputs, inadequate fertilizer uses and management, lack of extension services for sorghum, lack of preferred varieties and processing technologies. There is still lack of markets for farmers to sell their produce and unavailability of improved seed for farmers to purchase (Phiri *et al.*, 2019). In Zimbabwean rural areas the need for cash has made maize production to override the production of other crops that are suitable for those areas (Sodziwa, 2015). In these areas, maize can be traded easily to meet the financial obligations since it has a ready market. Most farmers fail to concede the relevance of sorghum as they are driven by the taste of maize (Dube, 2008). Sorghum production is also affected by poor prioritization of resources for instance some farmers especially communal farmers are unaware of fertilizer application in sorghum and they grow this crop on unfavourable parts of the arable land and also ignore the effective time of planting (Nziizah *et al.*, 2021). Despite the fact that sorghum has the potential to improve food security particularly in semi-arid and arid regions, research on sorghum is still lagging behind and the crop suffers an image problem since maize still remains the premier crop.

On the other hand, access to markets is also affected by poor road infrastructure between rural areas and the main urban markets. Only contract farmers have reliable transport and storage facilities since they are funded by private alcohol brewing companies. Consequently, in some rural areas the access to improved seed and new technologies is extremely limited. In these areas, the source of seed for farmers is mostly their own harvested seed, other farmers, from local grain markets and from the informal seed sector. Less than 10% of the total traditional grains (sorghum included) is handled by the formal market(Taremwa *et al.*,2016).

Generally, in Zimbabwe, there are no government policies that support the production, processing and use of traditional grain crops and this hinders sorghum production (Muzerengi and Tirivangasi, 2019). There are also no policies that favour the development of competitive markets that encourage small holder farmers to produce sorghum (Phiri *et al.*,2019). Lack of sorghum processing technologies is another factor that deters the development of formal markets. It takes longer to process sorghum using conventional processing technologies as compared to other crops like maize and this has greatly reduced sorghum's preference even by poor resourced communal farmers (Matthew, 2015). Policies that support increased production of sorghum should be implemented since sorghum does not only have the potential to increase food security to those in the semi-arid regions but can also stimulate the country's economic growth and development especially if the crop is processed into value added products. Sorghum is also capable of reducing the need for drought relief, lower the level of subsidies fundamental to grain markets and in the long run can curb rural to urban migration (Muzerengi and Tirivangasi, 2019).

High seed prices and poor seed quality limit further production of sorghum. Farmers need fair prices and companies need to feel confident to invest in farming (Sodziwa, 2015). Another important factor which acts as a production constraint towards sorghum is changing food preferences. It was noted that as consumers' income increase, they tend to purchase maize, rice, wheat and their products rather than sorghum. That being the case, producers then view sorghum as having lower returns than other enterprises (Matthew, 2015).

Sorghum still remains unattractive to farmers because it offers low yields. FAO (2010) alluded that the low yields of sorghum act as a major obstacle for farmers to expand production to a larger scale. In addition, Sodziwa (2015) noted that most sorghum varieties do not yield much crop

residue which is a disadvantage because crop residues are used as livestock feed during the winter season.

Although sorghum production has a lot of constraints, in the near future people especially those located in the arid region will be forced to produce it for survival because non-governmental organizations will find it difficult to continue providing them food if they are reluctant about producing it themselves.

2.10 Breeding of sorghum

The breeding efforts in sorghum are based on specific traits of interest and these traits vary from region to region where the majority of producers demand high yielding and stable varieties. On the other hand, resistance/tolerance to a specific abiotic stress or biotic stress is also required (Soko, 2016). Additionally, consumers require a certain grain quality depending on the growing environment and grain use. Thus, defining the breeding priorities according to the producers and consumers preferences is an important initial step in the implementation of a breeding program (Mofokeng, 2017). The wealth of genetic variability in sorghum germplasm has been and will continue to be exploited and utilized in breeding programs as a source of economically important traits. Breeding concepts and techniques are used to accelerate the perpetuation of sorghum varieties with high genetic yield potential to meet the diverse needs (Mofokeng, 2017). Molecular breeding is a powerful technique which combines breeding with genomic approaches to identify and select germplasm with desirable traits (Raza *et al.*, 2019). Molecular mechanisms responsible for stress tolerance in sorghum have been identified using Quantitative Trait Loci (QTL) studies, genomics and transcriptomic analyses. These analyses help to develop improved varieties with higher production potential under the ever-changing climatic factors (Masson-Delmotte *et al.*, 2019). Genome wide association studies (GWAS) has also been used in different crops for better

understanding of the genetic basis for stress tolerance under the influence of climate change and variability (Mousavi-Derazmahalleh *et al.*, 2018).

2.10.1 Importance of genetic diversity in sorghum breeding

Knowledge of the level of diversity in different germplasm is important for the identification of sources of improved breeding gene pools and the search for genes that have not been put into economic use (Warburton *et al.*, 2008). The use of diverse landraces by farmers is to address complex problems in their farming systems that include various stresses such as diseases, pests as well as drought and low soil fertility. Farmers prefer varieties with good yield but also with potential market value and stable under these stresses (Dossou-Aminon *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, availability of genetic diversity permits selection of germplasm that is stable and high yielding and with other traits preferred by farmers. This selection could be through heterotic groups or by use of molecular markers (Menz *et al.*, 2004). The identification of these groups and genetic distances may be based on several agronomic data and explored through multivariate analysis (Chikuta *et al.*, 2015).

2.10.2 Breeding for heat tolerance

Sorghum is a naturally heat tolerant crop but if the crop is heat stressed at critical stages it can result in reduced yield, therefore understanding the genetic control of heat tolerance is a prerequisite for developing an appropriate breeding program for sorghum. Studies have shown that heat tolerance in sorghum is associated with two genes (Khizzah *et al.*, 1993 and Chen *et al.*, 2017). Nagaraju *et al.*, (2015) conducted a genome wide analysis and they reported that sorghum expresses a number of heat shock transcription factors under heat stress and under drought stress. Johnson *et al.*, (2014) also reported that 17% of sorghum genes were differentially expressed for heat stress and 4% for drought stress and 7% of these unique genes exhibited combined stress response.

Exploitation of the unique genes can be used to improve sorghum for heat and drought stress tolerance under the prevailing changing climatic conditions.

2.10.3 Breeding for drought tolerance

Development of drought tolerant sorghum varieties stabilizes productivity and also provide sustainable production systems. To begin with, breeding for drought tolerant varieties entails an understanding of the environmental control over crop growth (Chadalavada *et al.*, 2021). Genomic regions related to drought tolerance in sorghum were identified by Tuinstra *et al.*, in 1997. Drought tolerant varieties show high photosynthetic efficiency and exhibit stay-green trait. The stay-green is said to improve yield under drought conditions (Chadalavada *et al.*, 2021). Genotypes exhibiting the stay-green trait have been used to develop new hybrids with enhanced drought tolerance (Borrell *et al.*, 2000, Jordan *et al.*, 2010 and Borrell *et al.*, 2014). Borrell *et al.*, (2014) further cited that the stay-green trait helps to reduce water uptake before flowering and assists the plant to use soil moisture during the grain filling stage to increase yield. Correspondingly genotypes with a stay-green trait exhibit charcoal rot and lodging resistance (Reddy *et al.*, 2007). It has also been found that root angle QTL is collocated with stay-green QTL and is linked to grain yield. CRISPR/Cas 9 systems can be used to characterize individual gene functions when expressed under stress conditions (Chadalavada *et al.*, 2021).

2.10.4 Breeding for cold tolerance

Sorghum is susceptible to cold stress and cold tolerant sorghum hybrids are very few worldwide hence improvement of early-stage cold tolerant hybrid is crucial breeding target for enhanced sorghum productivity (Chiluwal *et al.*, 2018). Some Chinese and Ethiopian germplasm have been identified as cold tolerant (Franks *et al.*, 2006 and Tifess *et al.*, 2020). Burrow *et al.*, (2011) identified Simple Sequence Repeats (SSR) markers linked with trait for cold tolerance. Tannin

free hybrids with early-stage cold tolerance and enhanced were also identified. These hybrids have extended flowering and grain filling staged which enables them to have enhanced grain yields with good quality (Ostmeyer *et al.*, 2020). Further research revealed that cold tolerance QTLs are co-mapped with tannin and dwarfing genes, so it important to cautiously comprehend how these traits are associated for further selection of cold tolerant cultivars. If the association is not well understood, selection can negatively affect grain quality (Marla *et al.*,2019).

2.10.5 Breeding for water logging tolerance

Breeding for water logging tolerance requires a proper understanding of molecular and physiological basis of this tolerance. Water logging tolerance mechanisms that have been observed in sorghum include, maintenance of high antioxidant activity (Zhang *et al.*, 2019b), nodal root development (Pardales *et al.*, 1991), formation of root parenchyma (Promkhambut *et al.*, 2011) and maintenance of high leaf-air temperature difference (Zhang *et al.*, 2019a). Breeding for varieties which exhibit these mechanisms is a requirement for improvement of cultivation of sorghum under water logging conditions.

2.10.6 Breeding for improved grain quality

Sorghum genotypes exhibiting the stay-green trait have been reported to also contain high nitrogen and nutritional qualities (Jordan *et al.*, 2012) and are said to have high sugar concentrations in their stems and leaves. Blummel *et al.*, (2015) discovered that stay-green sorghum is highly digestible. Moreover, studies by ICRISAT have shown stay-green trait can also enhance nutrient components such as starch, fats and proteins although this depends on the genetic background of the genotype. This breeding stay-green trait can help improve the nutritional quality of sorghum varieties along with drought tolerance.

Besides stay-green other studies have endeavored to improve sorghum grain quality by identifying mutants with unique grain composition. Promising mutant lines have been identified with high lysine content and high protein digestibility although these have undesirable floury endosperms (Tesso *et al.*, 2006). There is a possibility of improving these so that these have normal endosperms through the use of modern breeding techniques (Tesso *et al.*, 2006). Currently limited efforts have been made to develop agronomically adapted, high protein and digestible sorghum cultivars (Duressa *et al.*, 2018). Many researchers have observed large genetic variability for protein digestibility and protein content (Wong *et al.*, 2010, Elkonin *et al.*, 2013 and Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). This genetic variability is a potential source to breed cultivars with high protein digestibility and high protein content. Durra races of sorghum contain higher levels of protein (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017) and therefore potential breeding targets to develop cultivars with high protein content.

A transformation system was developed for sorghum by Lie *et al.*, (2014) which permitted the development of transgenic sorghum with improved starch content. Genetically modified sorghum lines can be used for the introgression of genes into locally adapted cultivars through breeding. Sorghum wild relatives exhibit a wide genetic variability and this can be used to improve cultivated sorghums' nutritional quality. For instance, Sudanese wild sorghum genotypes have elevated micro elements protein content, digestibility and lower tannins (Abdelhalim *et al.*, 2019). Some wild sorghum relatives are less affected by drought as compared to cultivated sorghums (Cowan *et al.*, 2019). Henceforth introgression of useful genes from the wild types to cultivated types can improve the nutrition quality of cultivated sorghum without compromising agronomical adaptability. The wide genetic diversity of sorghum and less genotype by environment (G×E) interaction allow for easy selection of desirable genotypes for particular environments (Kaufman *et al.*, 2018). However, grain physical traits such as grain weight and diameter are prone to G×E

interaction and therefore need to be carefully monitored while improving sorghum nutritional quality (Kaufman *et al.*, 2018). It is also necessary to study the stability the end-use quality traits of sorghum across different environments

2.11 Analysis of genetic diversity

2.11.1 Analysis of genetic parameter

Quantitative genetics is important for genetic breeding. Identification and multiplication of favourable genes of quantitative traits may be relatively easy if the selection is based on variance components and genetic parameters (Cruz *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, genetic parameters enable the detection of the action nature of genes involved. Genetic parameters also allow for the evaluation of efficiency of different selection methods (Cruz *et al.*, 2014). Selection criteria for superior genotypes depends on the characteristics of the crop and it requires basic information on the nature and extent of variation among genotypes and how the environment affects the expression of these characteristics contributing to yield. Genotypic variance, environmental variance and the interactions of the genotype and environment make up phenotypic variance (Badran , 2020). Use of variance to evaluate yield and all components that contribute to yield is key to a successful sorghum improvement program. Variability if traits among germplasm is assessed by evaluating genotypic coefficient of variance and phenotypic coefficient of variance and their interaction (Ahmed *et al.*, 2011). Estimating heritability is also important as heritability expresses genetic variance as a proportion of the total variation (Falconer, 1989). Heritability estimates are useful for calculating the expected genetic advance as a result of the selection of traits (Badran and Moustafa, 2015). The biplot is a graphical illustration that allows for conception of the interaction among genotypes and environments hence breeders use GGE biplot analysis for genotype evaluation (Yan and Kang, 2003).

2.11.2 Multivariate methods for genetic diversity analysis

There is a wide range of multivariate techniques that can be used for analysis of genetic diversity and the choice of the most suitable method depends on the type of data. Essentially, the analysis summarizes a large set of data by means of relatively few parameters (Kamuntu, 2010). The commonly used techniques are principal component analysis (PCA), cluster analysis and discriminant analysis (Murtagh and Heck, 2012). Principal component analysis (PCA) on inter-object correlations, reduction of their dimensionality and allows graphic presentation of the data, while cluster analysis is the application of automatic grouping procedures. Discriminant analysis classifies items into pre-defined groups (Murtagh and Heck, 2012). These methods have been used in many studies. For instance, principal component and cluster analysis were used to characterize sorghum germplasm based on morphological traits (Chikuta *et al.*, 2015). Chikuta *et al.* (2015) found that using PCA and cluster analysis on phenotypic traits, helps to classify genotypes according to their genetic similarities or differences. Moreover, results from PCA can be helpful in parent selection, thus breeding improvement Seetharam and Ganesamurthy, 2013).

2.12 Genotype main effects and Genotype by Environment Interaction (GGE) biplot analysis

Genotype by environment interaction is the differential response of two different genotypes to environmental variation (Yan *et al.*, 2007). The genotype by environment ($G \times E$) interaction has implication on the genotype's adaption and evaluation, where unpredictable environments and/or reduction of genetic variance increases selection in one direction. The $G \times E$ interaction is undesirable for breeders as it confounds genotype evaluation (Yan and Tinker, 2006). The $G \times E$ interaction is important in determining the relationship of the traits such as linear and non-linear regression (Mungra *et al.*, 2011). This interaction is higher in semi-arid tropics due to the variability of abiotic and biotic factors (Alagarwamy *et al.*, 1996). However, the adaptability of

the superior cultivars to certain environments is given by a cultivar superiority index where the lower value indicates general adaptation and higher value specific adaptation (Lin and Binns, 1988). This index can be used to measure performance and stability of a cultivar based on characteristics of the cultivar to allow better selections to be made.

A number of methods have been used to analyse multi-environment trial data and select superior genotypes for specific and wide adaptation. Methods such as additive main effects and multiplicative interaction (AMMI) (Gauch, 2006) and the genotype, genotype by environment (GGE) biplot method (Yan *et al.*, 2007) are usually used for exploring G×E in genotype evaluation. The AMMI model combines the analysis of variance and principal component analysis while GGE biplot is based on the principal component analysis (Gauch, 2006; Yan *et al.*, 2007). In the AMMI model, the main effects are retained as additive effects, while the G ×E interaction is treated as a multiplicative effect. Additional, Yan *et al.* (2007) reported that use of both GGE and AMMI analysis allows for the separation of genotype and genotype by-environment in mega-environment but GGE biplot is more superior than AMMI graph in mega-environment analysis. The GGE biplot uses the principal component scores to plot the effective view of multi-environment trial by showing “which-won-where” (Yan *et al.*, 2007). It has also been cited in a number of studies that GGE biplot is an exceptional method for visual data analysis (Yan and Tinker, 2006; Farshadfar *et al.*, 2012; Akter *et al.*, 2015).

2.13 Sectional conclusion

From the literature reviewed, it was noted that sorghum is widely produced in the world mainly in semi-arid areas of Africa and Asia where it is one of the most important staple foods. The yield of sorghum in most of the African countries is still very low due to a number of constraints. The wide genetic diversity of sorghum germplasm plays an important role in the improvement of cultivated

sorghum. Variability is important for genetic gain from selection and grouping lines into different heterotic groups. A better understanding of the phenotypic effects is still required to relate genotypic to phenotypic variation during crop improvement. Stable and high yields remain as important factors in the semi-arid and arid production environments where there is need of multi-environment trials analysis for selecting superior genotypes for wide or specific adaptation

CHAPTER THREE

GENETIC VARIABILITY OF SELECTED SORGHUM GENOTYPES BASED ON QUANTITATIVE TRAITS

3.1 Introduction

Genetic variability is important for continuing the process of evolution especially when farmers and breeders select crops for diversity in order to obtain desirable types that adapt to changing environmental conditions. Genetic diversity, therefore, is the foundation for crop improvement, it provides the raw materials from which desirable alleles for improved agronomic traits of interest can be selected and subsequently incorporated into elite lines. Breeders choose the traits that they want to breed for, for certain environments and these rely on the available genetic diversity that confers the trait diversity in the breeding populations (Akatwijuka *et al.*, 2016). Genetic variability is accessed through the use of morphological, biochemical and molecular characterisation approaches. Morphological characterisation is highly recommended because it is cheap and easy to carry out even on-farm. Studies have shown that results of morphological characterization are capable of identifying key descriptors that account for the majority of the variability observed (Bernado, 2010). The objective of this study was therefore to assess genetic variability of selected sorghum genotypes based on quantitative traits .

3.2 Materials and Methods

3.2.1 Experimental site

The experiment was carried out at Lupane State University Farm. Lupane State University is located at 170 km north of Bulawayo at 18°56'00"S and 27°46'00"E, 976 m above sea level in the Matabeleland North province. The area is characterized by hot dry weather conditions with an

average of 518 mm of rainfall per annum and average temperatures of 21.4°C. The rainy season is unimodal extending from mid-November to end of March. The dominant soils are the Kalahari sands and sandy loamy soils.

3.2.2 Experimental materials, design and procedures

Forty-nine sorghum genotypes/ accessions (Table 2) acquired from the National Genetic Resources and Biotechnology Institute of Zimbabwe and the International Crop Research Institute of the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT) Matopo were selected based on plant architecture and 100 grain weight from the previous season (2019/20) and these were used for the study. Three commercial sorghum varieties namely Macia, SV2 and SV were used as check genotypes. The genotypes were evaluated following a 7×7 alpha lattice design with two replicates. Each plot consisted of 4 rows of 5m length with in row spacing of 0.25m and inter-row spacing of 0.75m. Standard agronomic practices such as applications of fertilizers (Compound D and Ammonium Nitrate), weeding, pesticide application and thinning were adopted and applied at appropriate times during the entire crop production period as per recommendation of sorghum production. The genotypes planted under rainfed conditions and no irrigation was supplied to simulate low-input environments. Planting was done on the 2nd of December 2020. At harvest, two central rows within each plot were sampled for grain yield and converted to kilograms per hectare (kg ha⁻¹).

Table 2: sorghum genotypes, their identity, type and source used in the 2020/2021 evaluation season

Entry No	Genotype code	Genotype identity	Biological status	Locality/Province	Country of origin
1	ICR 54	IS 30008	Landrace	Hwange	Zimbabwe
2	ICR 123	IS 3996	Landrace	Kwazulu Natal	South Africa
3	Macia	Macia	Commercial variety	-----	-----
4	ICR 61	IS 13813	Landrace	Kwazulu Natal	South Africa
5	ICR 74	IS 29381	Landrace	Maseru	Lesotho

6	ICR 5	IS 35533	Landrace	Owambo	Namibia
7	SV 4	SV 4	Commercial variety	-----	Zimbabwe
8	GB 123	NGB 3110	Landrace	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
9	GB 15	NGB 3195	Landrace	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
10	ICR 19	IS 29925	Landrace	Hwange	Zimbabwe
11	GB 172	NGB 1695	Landrace	Murehwa	Zimbabwe
12	GB 175	NGB 1593	Research material	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
13	ICR 7	IS 6944	Landrace	-----	Sudan
14	SV 2	SV 2	Commercial variety	-----	Zimbabwe
15	ICR 142	IS 2419	Landrace	-----	Tanzania
16	ICR 28	IS 37158	Research material	Owambo	Namibia
17	ICR 65	IS 9548	Research material	-----	South Africa
18	GB 30	NGB 1862	Landrace	Nyanga	Zimbabwe
19	GB 56	NGB 3092	Landrace	Tsholotsho	Zimbabwe
20	ICR 34	IS 3574	Landrace	Kassala	Sudan
21	ICR 40	IS 23901	Landrace	-----	Yemen
22	ICR 20	IS 13904	Landrace	Kwazulu Natal	South Africa
23	ICR 21	IS 24272	Research material	-----	Tanzania
24	ICR 6	IS 10214	Research material	-----	France
25	ICR 14	IS 23908	Landrace	-----	Yemen
26	GB 98	NGB 1178	Research material	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
27	GB 61	NGB 3124	Landrace	Murehwa	Zimbabwe
28	GB 19	NGB 1260	Landrace	Tsholotsho	Zimbabwe
29	GB 92	NGB 3093	Research material	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
30	ICR 154	SS 2020	Landrace	Bubi	Zimbabwe
31	ICR 17	IS 9405	Landrace	Maseru	Lesotho
32	GB 13	NGB 3127	Landrace	Chipinge	Zimbabwe
33	GB 102	NGB 3133	Landrace	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
34	ICR 16	IS 30015	Landrace	Hwange	Zimbabwe
35	GB 137	NGB 3084	Research material	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
36	ICR 8	IS 30047	Landrace	Hwange	Zimbabwe
37	GB 185	NGB 1699	Research material	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
38	GB 136	NGB 1156	Landrace	Nyanga	Zimbabwe
39	ICR 1	IS 23843	Landrace	-----	Yemen
40	GB 43	NGB 3283	Landrace	Nyanga	Zimbabwe

41	ICR 116	IS 13837	Landrace	Kwazulu Natal	South Africa
42	GB 134	NGB 1698	Landrace	Tsholotsho	Zimbabwe
43	GB 2	NGB 3121	Landrace	Tsholotsho	Zimbabwe
44	GB 94	NGB 1759	Research material	Nyanga	Zimbabwe
45	GB 82	NGB 3102	Research material	Chiredzi	Zimbabwe
46	IGR 52	IS 26191	Landrace	Savanes	Togo
47	GB 124	NGB 3105	Landrace	Murehwa	Zimbabwe
48	GB 144	NGB 3087	Landrace	Murehwa	Zimbabwe
49	GB 88	NGB 1478	Landrace	Murehwa	Zimbabwe

3.2.3 Measurements and data collection

Quantitative data were recorded on days to 50% flowering, days to physiological maturity, plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf length, leaf width, stem diameter, plant count (number of plants per plot), number of productive tillers, number of non-productive tillers, exertion length, panicle length (head size), panicle weight (head weight) and grain yield per plot. Days to 50% flowering were counted from the day of sowing to when 50% of the plants had started flowering, displayed by the appearance of yellow anthers on the tip of the panicle. Plant height was taken using a tape measure from the base of the plant to the tip of the head at physiological maturity attained when a black-layer appeared above the point of grain attachment in the floret near the base of the grain. This was done on 5 randomly selected plants from middle rows in each plot. Number of leaves was determined by counting all leaves from first to the flag leaf from 5 randomly selected plants from middle rows in each plot. Leaf length data were taken from the base to tip of the leaf using a tape measure, leaf width was taken on the widest part of the same leaf also using a tape measure also from 5 randomly selected plants from middle rows in each plot. Plant count was determined by physically counting the plants that were in the sample plot. Number of productive tillers was determined by counting the number of tillers that had panicles containing grain, number

of non-productive tillers was determined by the number of tillers that did not produce any head. Exertion length was measured from the flag leaf to base of panicle from 5 randomly selected plants from middle rows in each plot, Panicle length was recorded by measuring each panicle from its base to its tip from 5 randomly selected plants from middle rows in each plot. Panicle weight was determined by weighing all the harvested panicles per plot before threshing and grain yield was determined by weighing the harvested grain after threshing and cleaning.

3.2.4 Data Analyses

General analysis of variance

General analysis of variance was performed for all quantitative data using the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) approach in R software using the Agricolae version 1.3-3 package (Mendiburu, 2020). Multiple comparisons among variety means were conducted by Fisher's Least significant difference (LSD) test at 5% levels of significance (Fisher, 1935).

Cluster analysis

Cluster analysis was based on Ward's clustering algorithm using Euclidean distances (Ward, 1963) and analyzed using the Multivariate program in the STAR statistical package version 2.01 (STAR v2.01) (IRRI, 2013).

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Analysis of variance for quantitative traits in 49 sorghum genotypes

The analysis of variance showed highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$) between genotypes in days to 50% flowering, plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf length and stem diameter. There were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between genotypes in days to physiological maturity,

leaf width and grain yield. No significant differences ($p>0.05$) were noted on traits such as number of productive tillers, number of non-productive tillers, plant count and head weight (Table 3). The coefficients of variation for plant count, head weight and grain weight were greater than 30 % showing variability for these traits among genotypes. Days to 50% flowering, day to physiological maturity, plant height, leaf length, leaf width, stem diameter, and head size had coefficients of variation less than 20% with days to 50% flowering having the least (7%) reflecting low variability in these traits (Table 3).

Table 3: Analysis of variance for 14 quantitative traits in selected sorghum genotypes

Source of variation	Mean \pm SE	Range	MS	%CV
Days to 50% flowering	82.23 \pm 4.01	59-130	592.64	7**
Days to maturity	118.5 \pm 14.63	92-165	743.50	17.5*
Plant height (cm)	241.2 \pm 18.64	112 – 130	6063.5	11.12**
Plant count	33.2 \pm 8.05	10 – 69	174.86	34.33 ^{ns}
No. of p tillers	0.34 \pm 0.40	0 – 2	0.34	162.26 ^{ns}
No. of non p tillers	0.22 \pm 0.34	0 – 2	0.30	216.29 ^{ns}
Number of leaves	13.35 \pm 0.83	8 – 19	15.07	8.75**
Leaf length (cm)	79.46 \pm 3.91	56 – 103	149.35	6.95**
Leaf width (cm)	7.62 \pm 0.69	5 – 11	2.28	13.2*
Stem diameter(mm)	19.01 \pm 1.59	11.5 - 27.3	16.59	11.86**
Exertion	6.51 \pm 2.0	0 - 26.8	66.21	43.38**
Head size (cm)	23.58 \pm 1.66	12 – 36	44.42	9.93*
Head weight (g)	2153 \pm 757.2	195 – 4700	1636550	49.7 ^{ns}
Grain yield (g)	2314 \pm 831.78	40 – 3628	893646	50.83*

MS=Mean Squares, %CV=Coefficient of variation, SE=Standard error, **, *,ns= highly significant ($p<0.001$), significant ($p<0.05$) not significant ($p>0.05$)

3.3.2 Cluster Analysis

Agglomerative hierarchical clustering performed on the Euclidean distance matrix utilizing Ward's linkage method and resulting dendrogram is presented in Figure 2. The forty-nine sorghum genotypes formed 4 clusters at 25% similarity level. Among the different clusters, the cluster size varied from 2 to 13. Cluster I composed of 12 genotypes and was further subdivided into 2 sub-clusters with 1a containing 3 genotypes and 1b containing 9 genotypes. Cluster II had the largest number of genotypes compared to other clusters and it was composed of 13 genotypes. The cluster was subdivided into 2 sub-clusters and 2a contained 2 genotypes while 2b had 11 genotypes. Cluster III was made up of 12 genotypes and was subdivided into 2 sub-clusters with sub-cluster 3a having 5 genotypes and 3b having 7 genotypes. Cluster 4 consisted of 12 genotypes and was also subdivided into 2 sub-clusters, sub-cluster 4a consisted of 3 genotypes while sub-cluster 4b consisted of 9 genotypes (Figure 2).

Table 4: Cluster membership of 49 sorghum genotypes derived from the Agglomerative method of hierarchical clustering

Cluster	Genotypes
1	IS 30008, Macia, IS 13813, IS 35533, SV 4, IS 2419, NGB 3094, IS 3574, IS 23901, NGB 3093, NGB 30047, NGB 1759
2	IS 13996, NGB 3195, IS 29925, IS 6944, IS 7158, IS 13904, NGB 1178, NGB 3124, NGB 1156, IS 23843, NGB 3283, IS 13837, NGB 3121
3	IS 9381, NGB 3110, NGB 1695, SV2, IS 9548, NGB 1862, IS 10214, NGB 3127, NGB 3133, IS 30015, NGB 3102, IS 26191
4	NGB 1593, IS 24272, IS 23908, NGB 1260, SS 2020, IS 9405, NGB 3084, NGB 1699, NGB 1698, NGB 1305, NGB 3087, NGB 1478

Separation of genotypes into clusters identified the most promising genotypes, specifically those that fell into cluster 1 and these were IS 30008, IS 13813, IS 35533, IS 2419, NGB 3094, IS 3574, IS 23901, NGB 3093, NGB 30047, NGB 1759. The check varieties used were macia, SV 2 and SV4. Macia and SV4 fell into the same cluster, that is, cluster 1 whereas SV2 fell into cluster 3 (Table 4).

Figure 2: Clustering of 49 sorghum genotypes into 4 cluster using the Agglomerative method of hierarchical clustering

Table 5: Comparison of quantitative traits of the four clusters of 49 sorghum genotypes derived from agglomerative clustering method

Variable	Cluster Means			
	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Days to physiological maturity	100.79	74.54	73.96	80.04
Plant height	275.25	240.46	224.54	228.04
Plant count	38.25	32.69	34.38	23.17
Productive tillers	0.25	0.19	1.04	0.00
Non-productive tillers	0.62	0.00	0.92	0.00
Number of leaves	16.92	1181	11.17	13.21
Leaf length	87.46	78.65	71.54	78.29
Leaf width	7.54	7.54	7.17	8.21
Stem diameter	21.66	17.68	15.51	20.76
Exertion	2.23	8.75	13.57	4.86
Head size	22.17	24.42	26.33	21.12
Head weight	1753.92	2689.15	2074.54	1493.92
Grain yield	1745.12	3149.92	2053.12	1559.38

Cluster means of the 4 similarity cluster groups in the 49 sorghum accessions are presented in Table 4. Genotypes in cluster 1 were characterized by tallest plants, more plants per plot, more and longer leaves per plant, thicker stems and late maturity (Table 5). Cluster 2 and 3 genotypes were similar in most traits except for head weight and grain yield where cluster 2 had the highest of these two traits with a yield of (3149.92 kg⁻¹ha). Cluster 4 genotypes had significantly low values virtually for all the traits including grain yield (1559.38 kg⁻¹ha) (Table 5).

3.4 Discussion

3.4.1 Analysis of variance for 14 quantitative traits in selected sorghum genotypes

Genotypes showed significant and highly significant variation in nearly all the measured traits except plant count, number of productive tillers, number of non-productive tillers and head weight. High magnitude of variation for the genotypes was also reflected by wider range for all the traits. Since the variation depends upon the magnitude of the measuring units of the traits, coefficient of variation is independent of the measuring units so it is more useful in comparing the population, the higher the coefficient of variation, the greater the dispersion in the variable. The high coefficient of variation values for the different quantitative traits also indicated high variability that exists in the genes of the evaluated sorghum genotypes. The significant differences indicated the existence of high degree of variability among the genotypes that could be exploited for sorghum improvement. Geleta *et al.*, 2006 observed that genetic variation among sorghum germplasm requires genetic resource collection, maintenance and utilization therefore grain yield which had a higher CV has the greater ability to be improved through selection. Generally, the mean grain yield of 2314g/plot (2263 kg ha⁻¹) was quite high compared to the average obtained grain yield of sorghum in Zimbabwe, this may be attributed to the good crop management of the sorghum genotypes during the study. The observed high variability for grain yield, exertion length, head size (panicle length), leaf width and leaf length were similar to earlier reports in sorghum by Elangovan *et al.* (2013) and Dossou-Aminon *et al.* (2015). Rao, et al. (1999) evaluated 4000 sorghum genotypes and they observed that days to 50% flowering, plant height and head size were highly variable among the genotypes and this concurred with the findings of the present study. Non-significant differences observed for some traits showed that the genotypes are genetically similar concerning these traits. Selecting for these traits will therefore show no impact on genetic

improvement. In contrast to the present study, Wasihun (2007) obtained results that showed that there was no significant difference among sorghum genotypes for days to 50% flowering.

3.4.2 Cluster Analysis using 13 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes

Cluster analysis grouped the 49 sorghum genotypes into four clusters. More similar and genetically closer genotypes were grouped together in the same cluster or sub cluster. The study picked out potential sorghum genotypes through Hierarchical Clustering using Ward's Euclidean distance method by grouping the potential lines in a single cluster. The clustering managed to separate potential sorghum genotypes namely: IS 30008, Macia, IS 13813, IS 35533, SV 4, IS 2419, NGB 3092, IS 3574, IS 23901, NGB 3093, NGB 30047, NGB 1759. The promising genotypes were characterized by tall plants, more plants per plot, more and longer leaves per plant, thicker stems, late maturity and significantly good yield. All clusters contained at least one high yielding genotype and this is an indication of a high level of diversity among the tested population. The same findings were observed by Mangena *et al* (2018) when they were evaluating sweet sorghum genotypes. The groupings may indicate that the genotypes from each group form a heterotic group meaning there is possibility of hybridizing genotypes from one cluster with genotypes from the other clusters to come up with new improved sorghum varieties. For instance, genotypes from cluster 1 can be hybridized with genotypes from cluster 2 to come up with genotypes with good crop stand, tall plants with more and longer leaves, thick stems and very high yielding.

CHAPTER FOUR

ESTIMATION OF GENETIC PARAMETERS AND EXPECTED GENETIC ADVANCE IN ASSEMBLED SORGHUM GERMPLASM

4.1 Introduction

For successful breeding programs, breeders should have a clear understanding variability using parameters like genetic co-efficient of variation, heritability and genetic advance. Heritability is measure of the phenotypic variance caused by to genetic factors and has predictive function in plant breeding. It provides information on the extent to which a particular trait can be passed on from one generation to another, and has an impact on the choice of selection procedures used by the plant breeder. Heritability helps breeders choose the most suitable selection methods that would be most useful to improve a particular trait, to predict gain from selection and to determine the relative importance of genetic effects (Tariq *et al.*, 2012). Researchers have reported that heritability is important in genetic studies of quantitative traits because it is capable of providing an indication of the reliability of phenotypic value as guide to breeding value. Traits with high heritability can easily be fixed with simple selection resulting in quick progress, but other studies have clarified that heritability alone has no practical importance without genetic advance. High genetic advance with high heritability estimates offers the most suitable condition for selection. The present study hence sought to estimate and evaluate genetic parameters and expected genetic advance in assembled sorghum germplasm in order to improve the yield of sorghum.

4.2 Materials and Methods

Refer to 3.2.1 up to 3.2.3

4.2.4 Genetic parameters analysis

Genetic parameters analysis The R software variability package version 0.1.0 was used for the analysis of genetic parameters. Genetic parameters determined were; genotypic variance (V_g) phenotypic variance (V_p), Broad sense heritability (H^2), genotypic co-efficient of variation (GCV) and phenotypic co-efficient of variation (PCV), genetic advance (GA) and genetic advance expressed as a percentage of means. The R package calculates the parameters basing on 25 methods by Hallauer and Miranda (1981), Singh and Chaudhary (1979) and Shukla et al. (2006) as follows:

1. Environmental variance (EV) = Error Mean Square (EMS)

2. Genotypic variance (GV) = Genotypic Mean Square (GMS) - Error Mean Square

Number of replications (r)

3. Phenotypic variance (PV) = Genotypic variance (GV) + Environmental variance (EV)

4. Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) = $\sqrt{\frac{V_G}{\bar{X}}} \times 100$

where $\sqrt{V_G}$ = Genotypic standard deviation and \bar{X} = population mean

5. Phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) = $\sqrt{\frac{V_P}{\bar{X}}} \times 100$

where $\sqrt{V_P}$ = Phenotypic standard deviation and \bar{X} = population mean

6. Heritability in broad sense (H^2) = $\frac{V_G}{V_P}$

7. Genetic advance, GA = $h^2 b.K. \sqrt{V_P}$

where h^2_b = Heritability in broad sense = $\frac{VG}{VP}$

\sqrt{VP} = Phenotypic standard deviation

K = Selection differential

$$8. \text{ Genetic Advance (\%)} = \sqrt{\frac{GA}{\bar{X}}} \times 100$$

Where \sqrt{GA} is genetic advance and \bar{X} = population mean

4.3 Results

Table 6: Genetic parameters for 9 quantitative traits of selected sorghum genotypes

Trait	Vg	Vp	GCV%	PCV%	H ²	GA	GA%
DMA	279.43	313.21	20.33	21.52	0.89	32.52	39.55
PHT	26.72	3391.65	11.12	21.43	0.79	94.51	39.19
NL	6.85	8.22	19.61	21.48	0.83	4.92	36.90
LL	55.80	86.32	9.400	11.69	0.65	12.37	15.57
LW	0.63	1.58	10.42	16.48	0.40	1.03	13.57
SD	5.45	10.54	12.29	17.08	0.52	3.46	18.20
EXT	29.11	37.10	82.75	93.43	9.84	9.84	150.99
HS	18.67	24.15	18.32	20.84	0.77	7.83	33.19
GYD	49.45	187.83	30.39	59.22	0.26	743.34	32.12

Vg= Genotypic Variance, Vp= Phenotypic Variance, GCV%= Genotypic Coefficient of Variance, PCV=Phenotypic Coefficient of Variance, H²= Heritability (Broad Sense), GA=Genetic Advance, GA%= Genetic Advance as percentage of mean, DMA=days to physiological maturity, PHT=plant height, PC=plant count, PT= number of productive tillers, NPT= number of non-productive tillers, NL= number of leaves, LL = leaf length, LW= leaf width, SD= stem diameter, EXT= exertion, HS= head size, HW= head weight, GYD= grain yield

Quantitative traits that had significant differences were analyzed for performance in relation to genetic parameters. The results show that there were significant differences between genotypic and phenotypic variance (Table 6). Phenotypic variance (V_p) estimates higher than those of genetic variance (V_g) for all the traits. Correspondingly, estimates for phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) were higher than those of genetic coefficient of variation (GCV) for all the traits. Grain yield (GYD) exhibited the highest genotypic and phenotypic variance, that is, 49.45 and 187.83 respectively followed by plant height which had a genotypic variance of 26.72 and phenotypic variance of 3391.65. The lowest genotypic and phenotypic variance was observed for the traits number of leaves (6.85 and 8.22 respectively) and leaf width (0.63 and 1.15 respectively). Genotypic coefficient of variance (GCV) and phenotypic coefficient of variance (PCV) were also calculated for the trait under study. Genotypic coefficient of variance ranged from 9.4 % (leaf length) to 82.75 (exertion) (Table 6). The broad sense heritability was high for days to physiological maturity, plant height, number of leaves, leaf length, exertion and head size ($H^2 > 0.6$). Broad sense heritability was moderate for leaf width (0.4) and stem diameter (0.52). The lowest heritability was scored for grain yield (0.26). The Genetic Advance expressed as a percentage of means for the traits ranged from 13.57% for leaf width and 150.99 % for exertion (Table 6).

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Genetic parameters for 9 quantitative traits

Genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation are used to estimate the influence of environmental factors on the expression of a trait in plant breeding programs. The difference between genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation indicates the level of environmental variations that plays an important role in trait expression (Mohan and Thiyagarajan, 2019). The

study exhibited significant genotypic and phenotypic differences among the genotypes under study. In the present study there was close correspondence between phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variation for traits such as days to physiological maturity, number of leaves per plant, leaf length, leaf width, stem diameter and head size indicating that there was less influence of environmental factors on the expression of those traits and the variation had a genetic origin. Similar results were obtained by Wuhaib *et al.*, 2017 where they observed that there were small differences between phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variation in sorghum varieties. However, more differences between phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variation were observed in traits such as plant height, exertion and grain yield indicating that the expression of these traits was more influenced by the environment. High genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation observed for the traits; days to physiological maturity, number of leaves per plant, exertion and grain yield indicated that selection can be applied on the traits to isolate more promising genotypes. Low genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation observed for the traits; leaf length, leaf width and stem diameter indicated that the breeders should go for source of high variability for these traits to make improvements in sorghum. A similar type of suggestion was given by Ravikesavan (2006). Observed variation in a population is due to both genetics and environmental factors whilst genetic variability is the only variability heritable from one generation to the next. The broad sense heritability was high for days to physiological maturity, plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf length, exertion and head size. For efficient selection we cannot solely rely on heritability but the combination of high heritability with high genetic advance provides a clear base on the reliability of that particular traits in the selection of variable genotypes since those traits are controlled by the additive genes and less influenced by the environment. High heritability and high genetic as a percentage of means was observed in days to

maturity, plant height, number of leaves and exertion. This indicated that these traits are highly reliable during selection process of the accessions (Ahsan, 2015). Grain yield had a low estimate of heritability but high genetic advance exhibiting grain yield variation is not due to genetic factors. Moreover, leaf length showed high heritability with low genetic advance indicating that this trait is controlled by non-additive gene action and it will have poor response to selection. Contrary to the current study, in a study carried out by Khandelwal *et al* (2015) it was observed that days to maturity and panicle length (head size) had high heritability but low genetic advance.

CHAPTER FIVE

TRAIT ASSOCIATION ANALYSIS IN SELECTED SORGHUM GENOTYPES

5.1 Introduction

The study of associations among quantitative traits is important for assessing the possibility of concurrent selection of two or more traits and henceforth for evaluating the effect of selection for secondary traits on genetic gain for the primary traits (such as yield) under consideration. Understanding associations among traits subsequently reduces time and funds invested in breeding programs (Lombardi *et al.*, 2015). It is easy to improve two traits simultaneously if there is a positive correlation between the traits (Ezeaku and Mohammed, 2006). Absence of correlation provides useful information for the joint improvement of the two traits. In contrast, a negative correlation between two desirable traits hinders significant improvement in both traits. Yield is a complex quantitative trait with low heritability and greatly depends on several other traits with high heritability. These traits are usually correlated and their interdependence influences their direct relation with yield. Information obtained on their association therefore becomes unreliable. Path coefficient analysis is therefore used to complement simple correlation analysis. Path coefficient analysis allows partitioning of correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects of various traits towards dependent variable (especially yield) and thus helps in assessing the cause-and-effect relationships among traits.

Principal component analysis aims at resolving the total variation of a set of traits into linear and independent composite traits, which is easily comprehensible. It is the most statistical tool used in variability studies and allows natural grouping of the genotypes according to their similarities or differences (Jolliffe and Cadima, 2016). Principal component analysis converts and analyzes a large set of variables into a relatively small set of variables or components without losing any essential

information of original data set. Since principal component analysis, extract all the important components and highlight their contribution toward the total variability, it is therefore an important tool to speed up the breeding programs (Karadi and Kajjidoni, 2020). In this context, the current study aimed to evaluate the traits having greater association with yield utilizing the correlation and path analysis for different traits in sorghum and also generate data on their performance using principal component analysis for further evaluation of sorghum.

5.2 Materials and Methods

Refer to 3.2.1 up to 3.2.3

5.2.4 Statistical Analyses

Correlation and path coefficient analysis

The Pearson's phenotypic correlation analysis and path coefficient analysis were performed using the Variability package version 0.1.0 for genetic variability analysis for plant breeding research (Popat et al., 2020) in R to describe the correlations among selected agronomic traits measured on selected sorghum genotypes. The significance of phenotypic correlation was tested using a two tailed t test.

Principal component analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of means for pooled quantitative data for all genotypes was conducted using the Multivariate analysis PCA function of the STAR statistical package version 2.01 (STAR v2.01) (IRRI, 2013).

5. 3 Results

5.3.1 Correlation analyses

The study revealed that there were only significant correlations between grain yield and plant count, leaf length, leaf width, stem diameter, head size and head weight. There was both positive and negative correlation among sorghum traits under study (Table 7). The strongest positive and significant correlation was observed between grain yield and head weight (0.87) followed by the correlation between days to 50% flowering and number of leaves (0.77). The results revealed that there a was moderately strong and significant correlation between number of leaves and leaf length (0.68), between stem diameter and number of leaves per plant (0.65) and also between leaf length and days to 50% flowering (0.62). There was a significant negative correlation between days to 50% flowering and grain yield and it was -0.62 (Table 7).

5. 3.2 Path coefficient analysis for grain yield

The path coefficient analysis for grain yield showed that head weight (0.80) had the highest positive direct effect on grain yield followed by leaf length (0.42). Days to physiological maturity had the highest negative direct effect on grain yield (-0.43) (Table 8). Head size had the highest indirect effect on head weight (0.55) whilst days to maturity had the highest negative indirect effect on leaf length (0.55) (Table 8).

Table 7: Correlation analysis of 14 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes

	DTF	DPM	PHT	PC	PT	NPT	NL	LL	LW	SD	EXTN	HS	HW	GYD
DTF														
DPM	0.573**													
PHT	0.471**	0.372**												
PC	0.083**	0.117ns	0.164**											
PT	0ns	0.053**	0.177**	0.368**										
NPT	0.011ns	0.035ns	0.121*	0.046ns	0.339**									
NL	0.769**	0.441ns	0.55**	0.088**	-0.01ns	0.036ns								
LL	0.621**	0.404**	0.443**	0.132**	-0.04*	-0.11ns	0.681**							
LW	0.06**	0.136**	0.044**	-0.164*	-0.1ns	-0.08ns	-0.03**	-0.05**						
SD	0.496**	0.209**	0.167**	-0.13**	-0.21ns	-0.147ns	0.65**	0.48**	0.002**					
EXTN	-0.23ns	-0.12ns	0.323**	-0.05**	0.17ns	0.236**	-0.34ns	-0.27*	0.008ns	-0.4ns				
HS	0.139**	0.127ns	0.096**	0.109**	-0.06ns	-0.036**	0.15**	0.01**	-0.01**	0.24**	-0.03**			
HW	-0.56ns	-0.38**	-0.21*	0.327**	0.145ns	0.029ns	-0.36ns	-0.17**	-0.15**	-0.23**	0.108*	-0.04*		
GYD	-0.62ns	-0.4ns	-0.28ns	0.309**	0.103ns	-0.101ns	-0.45ns	-0.22**	-0.15**	-0.28**	0.089ns	0.08**	0.87**	

DTF=days to 50% flowering, PHT=plant height, PC=plant count, PT= number of productive tillers, NPT= number of non-productive tillers, NL= number of leaves, LL = leaf length, LW= leaf width, SD= stem diameter, EXT= exertion, HS= head size, HW= head weight, GYD= grain yield. * = significant at (p<0.05), ** =significant at (p<0,001), ns = not significant (p>0.05)

Table 8: Path coefficient analysis showing direct (bold) and indirect effects of 12 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes on sorghum grain yield

	DMA	PH	PC	PT	NPT	NL	LL	LW	SD	EXTN	HS	HW
DMA	-0.4316	0.02224	0.0818	0.00523	-0.01489	-0.21648	0.23749	0.11354	0.03668	-0.00048	0.04339	-0.04761
PH	-0.30205	0.02811	0.08162	0.00969	-0.02664	-0.17895	0.20418	0.0709	0.028	-0.00507	0.05022	0.15678
PC	-0.15353	0.01128	0.14187	0.01345	-0.01562	-0.08658	0.11868	0.04993	0.01405	-0.00089	0.03713	0.41184
PT	-0.03225	0.0044	0.04418	0.0309	-0.04639	-0.01588	0.02032	-0.00342	0.00051	-0.0017	0.01021	0.13322
NPT	-0.02368	0.00312	0.01324	0.01196	-0.11863	-0.01581	0.00855	-0.00525	-0.00037	-0.00242	0.02233	0.05786
NL	-0.38501	0.02343	0.08204	0.00458	-0.01768	-0.24283	0.24388	0.11229	0.03996	0.00062	0.0461	0.09793
LL	-0.55434	0.03509	0.14758	0.00769	-0.01255	-0.32007	0.4249	0.20041	0.0598	-0.00219	0.10403	0.50365
LW	-0.33529	0.01542	0.07855	-0.00164	0.00975	-0.18646	0.25356	0.20058	0.0424	-0.00018	0.07883	0.30687
SD	-0.39342	0.02211	0.08026	0.00088	0.00249	-0.24098	0.27482	0.15402	0.05279	0.00029	0.0647	0.26944
EXTN	-0.0103	0.00808	0.01025	0.00598	-0.03285	0.00752	0.0203	0.00131	-0.00058	-0.00958	0.03434	0.14902
HS	-0.15773	0.01344	0.07191	0.00602	-0.05104	-0.09423	0.16201	0.09703	0.02193	-0.00577	0.12272	0.55161
HW	0.01318	0.0032	0.06075	0.00598	-0.01007	-0.01524	0.05974	0.02877	0.00695	-0.00191	0.04201	0.80924

DMA=days to physiological maturity, PHT=plant height, PC=plant count, PT= number of productive tillers, NPT= number of non-productive tillers, NL= number of leaves, LL = leaf length, LW= leaf width, SD= stem diameter, EXT= exertion, HS= head size, HW= head weight.

5. 3.3 Principal component analysis

Table 9: Principal components indicating standard deviation, proportion of variance and

Eigen values

Variables	PC 1	PC 2	PC 3	PC 4	PC 5
DMA	-0.3853	0.1773	-0.0947	0.0651	-0.1791
PHT	-0.2198	0.4316	-0.1159	-0.1966	0.3838
PC	0.0291	0.3681	0.2085	0.5454	-0.2230
PT	0.2256	0.2763	-0.1707	0.4538	-0.2741
NL	-0.4001	0.2288	-0.0019	-0.1752	-0.1536
LL	-0.3151	0.2897	0.2487	0.0581	-0.0610
LW	-0.0760	-0.4329	0.1455	-0.0061	-0.4933
SD	-0.3852	-0.0158	0.1338	-0.2707	-0.1499
EXT	0.3134	0.1611	-0.2962	-0.0974	0.2419
HS	0.2910	0.1020	-0.1002	-0.4298	-0.4232
HW	0.2709	0.2525	0.4959	-0.1988	0.0189
GYD	0.2533	0.1548	0.5757	-0.1825	0.0142
Standard deviation	2.1437	1.5394	1.2906	1.1227	1.007
Proportion of Variance	0.3535	0.1823	0.1281	0.0970	0.0780
Cumulative Proportion	35.35	53.58	66.39	76.09	83.89
Eigen values	4.5956	2.3697	1.6657	1.2606	1.0143

DMA = days to physiological maturity, PHT=plant height, PC=plant count, PT= number of productive tillers, NPT= number of non-productive tillers, NL= number of leaves, LL = leaf length, LW= leaf width, SD= stem diameter, EXT= exertion, HS= head size, HW= head weight.

The first five principal components PC1, PC2, PC3, PC4 and PC5 had Eigen values greater than one accounted for 83.92% of the total of the variation for all the traits (Table 9). The first principal component (PC1) accounted for 35.38% of the total variation. Days to physiological maturity, number of leaves per plant, leaf length, stem diameter and exertion were the main contributors. The second principal component (PC2) accounted for 18.23% of the total variation and the main contributing traits were plant height, plant count and leaf

width. The third principal component (PC3) accounted for 12.85% of the total variation. The key contributing traits of PC3 were head weight and grain yield. The fourth principal component (PC 4) accounted for 9.69% of the total variation with plant count where number of productive tillers and head size were the main contributors. The fifth principal component (PC5) accounted for 7.76% of the total variation and plant height, leaf width and head size were the key contributing traits (Table 9).

Figure 3 is a presentation of the principal component biplot analysis of 13 traits of 49 sorghum genotypes. The principal component biplot revealed that there was a significant correlation among the traits; head size (HS), exertion (EXTN), grain yield (GYD) and head weight (HW), there was also a significant relationship between days to physiological maturity (DMA) and number of leaves per plant (NL) in discriminating genotypes. There was no significant relationship between stem diameter (SD) and plant count (PC). According to the biplot plant height (PHT), leaf length (LL), number of leaves (NL), days to physiological maturity (DMA), stem diameter (SD) and leaf width (LW) were negatively correlated to grain yield (GYD). Genotype 27 (NGB 3124) was one of the best performers in grain yield. Genotype 46 (IS 26191) had long exertion, genotype 34 (IS 30015) had the long heads, genotype 21 (IS 23901) had tall plants, genotype 1 (IS 30008) had the most leaves per plant and matured late (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Biplot analysis of 13 quantitative traits of 49 sorghum genotypes(arranged by their plot number) evaluated.

5. 4 Discussion

5.4.1 Correlation analysis

The study showed significant and positive correlation amongst some sorghum traits. The strong positive correlation observed between grain yield and head weight indicated that as the mean values of head weight increased, grain yield also increased implying that selection of any one trait will result in the improvement of the other. Late flowering genotypes had thicker stems and more leaves meaning they allocated more synthetases to vegetative growth before they began to flower (Chopart *et al.*, 2008). The moderately strong correlation between days to flowering and days to physiological maturity showed that those genotypes which flowered early also matured early and those that flowered late also matured late, Mangena et al (2018) made similar reports. The strong negative correlation between days to flowering and grain yield indicated that as the days to flowering increased, grain yield decreased and as days to flowering decreased, grain yield increased. The negative correlation observed between the three leaf associated traits namely; number of leaves per plant, leaf length and leaf width and grain yield differed from what was observed by Sinha and Kumaravadivel (2016) and Khandelwal *et al* (2015). The lack of correlation between and among traits for example between days to flowering and number of productive and non-productive tillers provided useful information that the traits can be concurrently improved (Ezeaku and Mohammed, 2006).

5.4.2 Path coefficient analysis

Path coefficient analysis has been used to evaluate selection criteria in crops. Path coefficient analysis helps to determine the direct impact of one variable on another and partition the correlation coefficient into its component of direct and indirect impacts. Furthermore, partitioning of correlation coefficients into direct and indirect effects gives a true nature of association between

observed traits (Walle *et al.*, 2018). The high positive direct effect of head weight and leaf length on grain yield observed in the present study meant that for breeding purposes, head weight and leaf length selection will lead to a higher genetic gain in grain yield. Among the quantitative traits studied, high positive indirect effects of head weight on head size and leaf length indicates that indirect selection for grain yield in sorghum can be utilized through head size and leaf length.

5.4.3 Principal component analysis (PCA)

Principal component analysis was performed in order to reduce the large set of traits to a more meaningful smaller set of traits and to know which trait is contributing to maximum variability, because genetic improvement depends on the magnitude of genetic variation (Fenty, 2004). In this study, the traits revealed by the first five principal components accounted for the largest variability and were similar to those identified under cluster analysis. In these five PCAs, NL, EXT, PHT where the greatest contributors to variation which suggest greater more potential for improvement of these traits using this germplasm. This showed that PCA is a reliable method in identifying few key traits contributing to the largest variation and could be a reliable method in predicting the important traits influencing clustering of different genotypes observed. The findings were contrary to the findings made by Mulima, (2017) who concluded that days to 50% flowering and grain weight were the major contributors to the total variation in the first five PCAs. In the current study, the first five principal components had eigen values greater than 1 and they accounted for a higher percentage of the total variation (83.92%). These results were not in agreement with the findings of Tesfaye, (2017) who reported that only the first four principal components had eigen values greater than 1 and explained about 71.9% of the total variation among accessions for all traits.

Principal component biplot analysis illustrated the association among traits and also how the genotypes associate with the traits. Significant correlation of traits in discriminating genotypes was

observed from traits that had a small angle between dimension vectors in the same direction. A 90° angle showed that there was no significant relationship among traits. According to biplot analysis an obtuse angle indicates negative correlation and this was confirmed by the results obtained in the present study. Genotypes that excelled in a particular trait were plotted closer to the vector line and further in the direction of that vector. The biplot gave a clear indication that there was genetic diversity among the sorghum genotypes since different genotypes excelled in different traits, the same views were upheld by Tesfaye, (2017).

CHAPTER SIX

GENOTYPE MAIN EFFECTS PLUS GENOTYPE BY ENVIRONMENT INTERACTION FOR GRAIN YIELD IN SELECTED SORGHUM GENOTYPES ACROSS THREE ENVIRONMENTS

6.1 Introduction

Most breeders conduct multi-environmental trials to select for high yield stability and broad adaptation at the final stage of variety development (Djurovic *et al.*, 2014). Multi-environmental trials are important for predicting and estimating yield potential, identifying stable and most adapted genotypes for a particular environment. The observed performance of a particular genotype is a result of the genotype's genetic makeup (G), the environment (E) in which it grows and the interaction of both two components (GEI) and this results in the selection or non-selection of such a genotype (Akter *et al.*, 2015). Performance of genotypes is variable in different environments due to genotype by environment (G×E) interactions. However, (G×E) interactions complicate and impair selection of many traits since they are expressed differently in different environments (Djurovic *et al.*, 2014). These interactions also minimize the size of the association between phenotypic and genotypic rates (Mohamed, 2013). Nzuve *et al.*, (2013) reported that G×E interactions reduce heritability of quantitative traits and that it is therefore, vital to conduct multi-environmental trials to quantify G×E interactions in order to precisely account for the interactions before any effective selection is carried out. Multi-environmental trials are carried out not only to quantify G×E interactions but also to match genotypes to their most suitable environments (Yan and Tinker, 2006).

For proper assessment of G×E interactions, more advanced statistical methods than the standard analysis of variance (ANOVA) are required. Use of the standard ANOVA for G×E interactions is

improper because ANOVA assumes that the different environments homogeneous and does not account for non-additive terms (Mitrovia *et al.*, 2012). The additive main effects and multiplicative interactions (AMMI) and genotype (G) and genotype-by-environment interaction biplot analysis (GGE-biplots) (Yanand Tinker, 2006) methods are thus used to assess GXE interaction effects. AMMI breaks down the interaction into its separate components for each environment. The interactions are compressed into principal components depending on the number of significant interactions (Bose *et al.*, 2014). However, AMMI cannot be used to identify superior genotypes or suitable environments and this is where GGE biplot analysis is incorporated. GGE biplots can be used to identify superior and stable genotypes with specific adaptation to certain environments (Gerrano *et al.*, 2020). GGE biplots evaluate grain yield and stability using average environment coordination (AEC). The AEC is defined by the average principal component scores for all the environments (Dehghani *et al.*, 2009). Since both the AMMI and GGE approaches depend on principal component analysis (PCA), high-dimensional data becomes difficult to interpret visually in biplot analysis and so breeders have to plot a number biplots in order to be able to interpret enough of the original G×E interactions variability (Neisse *et al.*, 2018). In recent years, the quantification of G×E interactions and yield stability studies involving several cereal crops have been done (Benin *et al.*, 2012, Carvalho *et al.*, 2016, Machado *et al.*, 2019). Hence, the objective of the present study was to deduce G×E effects on sorghum grain yield and select adaptable genotypes with high and stable yield across three locations in Zimbabwe.

6. 2 Materials and Methods

6. 2.1 Experimental sites

The experiment was carried out in Zimbabwe at three sites (Table 10) which are; Lupane State University (18°56'20.76" S and 27°45'20.13"E) with an elevation of 976m above sea level,

Matopo Research Station (20°23'05.08"S and 28°30'52.69"E) with an elevation of 1351m above sea level and Gwebi Variety Testing Centre (17°40'60"S and 30°52'0"E) and is at 1450m above sea level. The trials were done under rain fed conditions in the 2020/21 rainfall season. Lupane State University and Matopo Research Station are located Natural Region IV which is characterized by semi-arid climatic conditions with annual rainfall ranging from 450mm to 650 mm per annum. Rainfall season is unimodal and begins in November or December and ends in March or April. The cropping season experiences periodic dry spells particularly in January and March. It is followed by a cool to warm dry season from May to September. Gwebi Variety Testing Centre is located in Natural Region IIB. The rainfall ranges from 700 to 1 000 mm/year. It is fairly reliable but can be sometimes unevenly distributed, falling from November to March/April.

Table 10: Description of sites used to evaluate G×E effects on sorghum grain yield

Code	Location	Altitude	Longitude/latitude	Soil type
E1	Matopo	1351m	20°23'05"S and 28°30'52"E	clay loamy
E2	Gwebi	1450m	17°40'60"S and 30° 52'00"E	sandy clay loams
E3	Lupane	976m	18°56'00"S and 27°46'00"E	sandy loamy

6. 2.2 Experimental materials, design and procedures

Refer to 3. 2. 2

6.2.3 Data Analyses

Data was pooled across locations and subjected to an analysis of variance to deduce the genotypic performance across environments. Subsequently, the Additive Main Effects and Multiplicative Interaction (AMMI) model was performed to deduce stable and high yielding genotypes using

GenStat 13th Edition software (Payne *et al.*, 2010). GGE analysis was applied to determine stability and adaptability of sorghum genotypes grown in three environments for grain yield measured as kilograms per hectare. GGE biplot analysis was done using GenStat 13th Edition software (Payne *et al.*, 2010). The Plant Breeding Tools (PBTools) statistical package (IRRI, 2013) was used to plot the ‘AMMI GGE biplot for sorghum grain yield and the ‘discriminating power and representativeness’ view of the GGE biplot.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Analysis of variance for grain yield

The AMMI analysis revealed that the trial environments and the genotypes were diverse ($P < 0.05$) however their genotype by environment interaction effects had no significant impact on yield performance ($P > 0.05$) (Table 11). The AMMI model further partitioned the interaction sum of square into interaction principal component axes 1 and 2 (IPCA 1 and IPCA 2, respectively) and residual term. Additional analysis of the genotype by environment interaction (GEI) using the PCA (interaction principal components) analysis confirmed that there was no statistical significance of the first two principal components, IPCA 1 and IPCA 2 (Table 11). Separately, IPCA1 and IPCA2 participated in the GEI variation, with 64.7% and 24.93%, respectively both without a statistically significant effect on the GE interaction variation (Table 11).

Table 11: AMMI analysis of variance for sorghum grain yield (Kg ha⁻¹) of 49 sorghum genotypes evaluated across three locations of Zimbabwe

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	Fprob
Total	293	660313434	2253629	*	*
Treatments	146	501882829	3437554	3.22	0.00000
Genotypes	48	253161125	5274190	4.94	0.00000
Environments	2	132766048	66383024	43.10	0.00000
Block	6	4620311	1540104	1.44	0.23310
Interactions	96	115955656	1207871	1.13	0.25035
IPCA 1	49	72171547	1472889	1.38	0.07454
IPCA 2	47	43784109	931577	0.87	0.70090
Error	144	153810294	1068127	*	*

6.3.2 Genotype evaluation by AMMI biplot

The results of the study revealed that genotypes G44 (IS 10214), G17 (NGB 1862), G15 (NGB 1260), G50 (Macia), G49 (IS 30047), G48 (IS 9381), G12 (NGB 1695), G9 (NGB 3084), G52 (SV 4), G32 (SS 2020), G1 (NGB 1260) and G26 (IS 29925) adapted well to environments E2 (Gwebi) and E3 (Lupane). Genotype G26 (IS 29925) was the highest in terms of yield performance in environment E3 (Lupane) and genotype G40 (IS 23901) was one of the best in environment E2 (Gwebi). Genotypes G5 (NGB 3105), G3 (NGB 3133), G37 (IS 24272), G38 (IS 37158), G19 (NGB 3092), G40 (IS 23901), G7 (NGB 1698), G20 (NGB 3124) and G29 (IS 13996) performed well in both environments E1 (Matopo) and E2 (Gwebi) with G40 (IS 23901) being specifically

Environment	Mean	Score	1	2	3	4
E3	2314	34.93	ICR 19	SV 2	SV4	GB 98
E2	1558	28.24	ICR 61	Macia	GB 175	ICR 40
E1	3202	-63.17	GB 92	ICR 123	SV 2	GB 61

Table 14 supports what is shown in figure 3. Results of yield of the environments and their respective scores on the first axis of GEI picked out the first four best performing genotypes in the respective environments. The results showed that in environment 1 (Matopo), genotype GB 92 (NGB 3093) could be considered as the best performing genotype since it ranked first followed by ICR 123 (IS 13996). In environment 2 (Gwebi), genotype ICR 61 (IS 13813) was the best performing genotype and in environment 3 (Lupane) genotype ICR 19 (IS 29925) was the most promising genotype in terms of yield. In all the three environments, the check varieties were outperformed by the test genotypes. In environments 2 and 3, Macia and SV 2 ranked second respectively while in environments 1 and 3, SV2 and SV 4 ranked third respectively (Table 12).

6.3.3 Comparison of environments based on the concentric circle

The environment comparison using Average Environment Axis (AEA) revealed that planting in environment 1 (Matopo) provided the most ideal conditions for sorghum production (Figure 5). Environment 3 (Lupane) was the next most suitable environment and environment 2 (Gwebi) was the least ideal environment (Figure 5). The GGE biplot also compared the genotypes with the ideal genotype located at the epicenter of the concentric circles. Genotypes that are plotted close to the epicenter are considered to be close to the ideal genotype in terms of yield production and stability

averaged across environments. The genotypes with performance close to the ideal genotype at the epicenter were 14 (SV 2) and 29 (NGB 3093) (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The Average Environment coordination (AEC) view of the GGE biplot ranking genotypes (replicated two times) and environments relative to the center of the concentric circles.

6.3.4 Delineation of environments and superior genotypes

Figure 6: A ‘which-won-where’ GGE biplot based on a genotype by environment grain yield data of the 49 sorghum genotypes and evaluated in three environments

The GGE biplot which was made up of two principal components; principal component (PC) axis 1 explained 75.22% of the total variation and principal component axis 2 explained 16.18% , in total accounting for 91.40% of the total variation for grain yield (Figure 6). The environments were clustered into two of the three sectors depicted by the GGE bi-plot (Figure 6). Environments 2 and 3 were clustered into one sector and formed one mega-environment, while environment 1 was considered as a separate individual environment. The GGE bi-plot also identified genotypes that had specific adaptation and high yield in the respective environments. The genotypes located at the vertices of the polygon were ICR 123 (IS 13996), SV2, GB 19 (NGB 1260), SV4 and GB 92 (NGB 3093). Genotype SV 2 was the best performing and most adapted genotype for the mega-environment comprised of environments 2 and 3. Genotypes ICR 123 (IS 13996), GB 19 (NGB 1260), SV4 and GB 92 (NGB 3093) were on the vertices of unclustered environments (Figure 6).

6.3.5 Environment evaluation by GGE biplot

The plot in Figure 6 enables evaluation of the test environments, to identify environments that may serve to select superior genotypes in an efficient way for a mega-environment. Environment E1 (Matopo) had the longest vector meaning it had high discriminating power for the genotypes followed by environment E3 (Lupane). Environment E2 (Gwebi) had the least discriminativeness in relation to genotypes. By using the information depicted in figure 7, it was possible to identify environments with representativeness in this case it was E2 (Gwebi) since this environment had a smaller angle between itself and the Average Environment Axis (AEA) (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Discriminativeness vs Representativeness" GGE biplot for the 3 environments in the study

6.4 Discussion

6.4.1 Genotype main effects plus genotype by environment interaction for grain yield in selected sorghum genotypes across three environments

The AMMI analysis revealed that the trial environments and the genotypes were diverse with high differences among their means, causing variation on grain yield of sorghum, however their genotype by environment interaction effects had no significant impact on grain yield. Gerrano *et*

al., (2020) also propounded that genotype and location (environment) had significant effects on yield of cowpeas. The traits with a high degree of variability in agronomic and economic importance are considered simultaneously in crop improvement programs due to the genetic correlations that exist among traits. Improving the traits of interest would result in improvement of the other traits. The sorghum genotypes exhibited a considerable level of variation for grain yield due to differences in genetic constitution or influence of the environment since yield is quantitatively inherited. The diversity exhibited by the genotypes in this study is useful in selection of parental lines for breeding programs and further improvement of sorghum towards exploiting heterosis when developing hybrids. The changes in genotype performance across different environments reduce the relationship between genotypes and their corresponding phenotypes (Aramendiz *et al.*, 2019). The genotype and environment had a non-significant interaction on grain yield suggesting that the different sites exerted similar pressure on genotype performance. This could help to reduce breeding costs, as genotypes selected for one environment could be suitable for other environments too.

Genotype valuation by AMMI biplot for yield revealed the genotypes that performed well in the respective environments. AMMI analysis ranked the most promising genotypes within the first four AMMI selections in the respective environments implying that these genotypes had best adaptability to the respective environments. However, a number of genotypes were less responsive to the three environments.

Matopo was revealed to be the most ideal environment for sorghum production because this environment was closest to the epicenter of the concentric circles of the comparison plot for environments. The ideal environment offers the highest discriminatory ability (Gerrano *et al.*,

2020). Gwebi was deemed to be the least ideal environment because it was distal to the epicenter of the comparison plot however it was the most consistent environment for sorghum production.

The polygon connected genotypes ICR 123 (IS 13996), SV2, GB 19 (NGB 1260), SV4 and GB 92 (NGB 3093) showing that these genotypes were farthest from the origin and adapted to specific environments. The rest of the genotypes were contained within the polygon as they had shorter vectors than the vertex genotypes and were less affected by the influence of a particular environment. Yan and Rajcan (2002) emphasized that genotypes with shorter vectors are less responsive to the genotype \times environment interaction exerted by a particular environment. The three test environments were delineated into two showing that 2 environments, that is, Lupane and Gwebi were correlated into 1 mega environment. Genotypes ICR 123 (IS 13996), GB 19 (NGB 1260), SV4 and GB 92 (NGB 3093) were on the vertices of unclustered environments hence they exhibited no specific adaptation to any environment. These results concur with the findings of Gerrano et al,(2020) who reported that some cowpea genotypes were adapted to the test environments whilst others did not show specific adaptation to the environments. The clustering of environments into a single mega-environment is important because it allows for simultaneous selection of genotypes for the environments within the same mega-environment. Simultaneous selection is acceptable because environments in the same mega-environment are positively correlated (Yan et al., 2000) and this reduces costs associated with breeding. In this study environments 2 (Gwebi) and 3 (Lupane) formed one mega environment showing that for a single season evaluation, either of the environments can be used as a testing site. The environments were grouped according to the prevailing environmental conditions meaning, climatic and soil conditions played a major role in delineating the environments.

CHAPTER SEVEN

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The aim of this study was to enhance full utilization of sorghum germplasm collections in breeding programmes and thus strengthen sorghum production and productivity in marginal areas of Zimbabwe through; assessing genetic variability of selected sorghum genotypes based on quantitative traits, estimating genetic parameters and expected genetic advance in assembled sorghum germplasm and evaluation of trait association in selected sorghum genotypes. The study also evaluated sorghum genotypes under three different environments in Zimbabwe and provided a basis to understand genotype and environmental influences on agronomic performance of sorghum.

The present study revealed a high degree of variability among the selected sorghum genotypes and the variability could be exploited for sorghum improvement. Exertion had the highest heritability but the trait of great economic importance which had the highest heritability was days to physiological maturity. Selecting sorghum genotypes with head weight can lead to improvement in grain yield. The three test environments; Matopo, Gwebi and Lupane were diverse although Gwebi and Lupane formed one mega environment.

When breeding for grain yield in sorghum it is recommended that genotypes which have high head weight, longer heads (panicles) be selected since they are correlated to grain yield. Selections can be made from either Matopo or Lupane. Genotypes NGB 3093, IS 13813 and IS 29925 give the highest grain yield and need to be considered for further evaluation.

In the future it is recommended that genetic analysis should also be done by making use of molecular markers since these reflect more accurate genetic variability since they are direct

products of genes and are not affected by environment. They also have the potential to give results within a short period of time.

REFERENCES

- A. Adugna (2014). “Analysis of in situ diversity and population structure in Ethiopian cultivated *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) landraces using phenotypic traits and SSR markers,” SpringerPlus 3 (1): 1–14.
- Rao. V. R and Hodgkin. T (2002). Genetic diversity and conservation and utilization of plant genetic resources. *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture* 68: 1–19
- Abdelhalim. T. S, Kamal. N. M and Hassan. A. B (2019). Nutritional potential of wild sorghum: grain quality of Sudanese wild sorghum genotypes (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench). *Food Science and Nutrition* 7(4):1529–1539
- Abe Shegro Gerrano, Maryke Tine Labuschagne, Angeline van Biljon and Nemera Geleta Shargie (2014). Genetic diversity assessment in sorghum accessions using qualitative morphological and amplified fragment length polymorphism markers. *Scientia Agricola* 71(5): 345-355.
- Ahmad. S.Q, Khan. S, Ghaffar. M and Ahmad. F (2011). Genetic diversity analysis for yield and other parameters in maize (*Zea mays* L.) genotypes. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 3 (5): 385–388.
- Ahsan. M. Z, Majidano. M. S, Bhutto. H, Soomro. A. W, Panhwar. F. H, Channa. A. R and Sial. K. B (2015). Genetic Variability, Coefficient of Variance, Heritability and Genetic Advance of Some *Gossypium hirsutum* L. Accessions. *Journal of Agricultural Science* 7 (2): 147-151.
- Akatwijuka. R, Rubaihayo. P. R and Odong. T. L (2016). Genetic diversity among sorghum landraces of Southwestern highlands of Uganda. *African Crop Science Journal* 24(2): 179-190. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/acsj.v24i2.6>

Akter. A, Hasan. M. J, kulsum. M. U, Rahman. M. H, Paul. A. K, Lipi. L. F and AKTER. S (2015). Genotype \times Environment Interaction and Yield Stability Analysis in Hybrid Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) By AMMI Biplot. Bangladesh Rice Journal, 19 (2): 79-86.

Akter. A, Hasan. M. J, Kulsum. U, Rahman. M. H., Khatum M and Islam M. R (2015). GGE Biplot Analysis for Yield Stability in Multi-environment trials of Promising Hybrids Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). Bangladesh Rice Journal 19(1):1-8.

Alagarwamy. G, Van Oosterom. E, Sethi. S, Cooper. M and Hammer. G (1996). International multi-environment trials at the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT). Plant Adaptation and Crop Improvement edition. Cooper, M and GL Hammer. p165-174.

Ali. S. B. M. and Mahdi. A. A (2017). Biocontrol of *Striga hermonthica* (Del.) Benth. in Sorghum. Journal of Faculty of Education 1:14-24.

Amelework. B, Shimelis. H, Tongoona. P and Laing. M (2015). Physiological mechanisms of drought tolerance in sorghum, genetic basis and breeding methods: A review. African. Journal Agricultural Research 10(31): 3029-3040.

Aramendiz. T. H, Miguel. E. C and Carlos. C. A (2019). Adaptation and stability of cowpea ('*Vigna unguiculata*' (L.) Walp) bean cultivars in the tropical dry forest of Colombia. Australian Journal of Crop Science 13:1009–1016

Aruna. C, Bhagwat. V. R, Vittal. S, Hussain. T, Ghorade. R. B and Khandalkar. H. G (2011). Genotype X Environment interactions for shoot fly resistance in sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.)

Moench]: response of recombinant inbred lines. *Crop Protection* 30: 623-630. Doi 10.1016/j.cropro.2011.02.007.

Assefa. Y, Staggenborg. S. A and Prasad. V. P. V (2010). Grain sorghum water requirement and responses to drought stress: A Review. *Crop Management*. 10: 1109-1116.

Badran. A. E (2020). Genetic parameters of some sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) genotypes under water deficit stress. *Egyptian Journal of Desert Research.*, 70 (2): 103-119

Badran. A.E. and Moustafa E.S.A.(2015). Genetic parameters of some wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotypes using factorial mating design. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 7 (1): 101-105

Barrett. C. B and Maxwell. D.G (2005). *Food Aid After Fifty Years: Recasting Its Role*. Routedledge, New York.

Benin. G, Bornhofen. E, Beche. E, Pagliosa. E. S, Silva. C. L and Pinnow. C (2012). Agronomic performance of wheat cultivars in response to nitrogen fertilization levels. *Acta Scientiarum. Agronomy*, 34 (3): 275-283.

Bernardo. R (2010). *Breeding for quantitative traits in plants*. Second Edition. University of Minnesota-Twine cities. Stemma Press, Woodbury, Minnesota, USA.

Beyene. Y, Botha. A. M and Myburg. A. A (2005). A comparative study of molecular and morphological methods of describing genetic relationships in traditional Ethiopian highland maize. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 4: 586-595.

Bhanderi. G, Sandipan. P.B and Patel. K (2015). Study of Various Fungicides Against Ergot Disease of Sorghum Caused by *Claviceps sp.* Under South Gujarat Condition. Trends in Biosciences 8:5671-5674

Bie. S, Kong. F.L, Zho. Y.Y, Zhang.G.M and Wang. X.G (2001). varieties in three main cotton regions in China by RAPDs and its relation with agronomic characters. *Scientia Agricultura Sinica* 34: 597-603.

Borrell. A. K, Hammer. G. L and Henzell. R. G (2000). Does maintaining green leaf area in sorghum improve yield under drought? II. Dry matter production and yield. *Crop Science* 40:1037–1048

Borrell. A. K, Mullet. J. E, George-Jaeggli. B, Oosterom. E. J, Hammer. G. L, Klein. P. E and Jordan. D. R (2014). Drought adaptation of stay-green sorghum is associated with canopy development, leaf anatomy, root growth, and water uptake. *Journal of Experimental Botany.* 65:6251-6263.

Bose. L. K, Jambhulkar. N. N and Singh. O. N (2014). Additive main effects and multiplicative interaction (AMMI) analysis of grain yield stability in early duration rice. *Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences* 24(6):1885–189.

Boyles R E, Brenton ZW, Kresovich S (2019). Genetic and genomic resources of sorghum to connect genotype with phenotype in contrasting environments. *The Plant Journal* 97: 19-39.

Buschmann. M (2018). Diversity of sorghum. Second European Sorghum Congress 2018.

Carvalho. I. R, Nardino. M, Demari. G. H, Bahry. C. A, Szareski. V. J, Pelissari. G, Ferrari. M, Pelegrin. A. J, Oliveira. A. C, Maia. L. C and SOUZA. V. Q (2016). Bi-segmented regression,

factor analysis and AMMI applied to the analysis of adaptability and stability of soybean. *Australian Journal of Crop Science*, 10 (10):1410-1416.

Chadalavada. K, Kumari. B. D. R and Kumar. T. S (2021). Sorghum mitigates climate variability and change on crop yield and quality. *Planta* 253:113 doi.org/10.1007/s00425-021-03631-2

Chakauya. E, Tongoona.P, Matibiri. E. A and Grum. M (2006). Genetic Diversity Assessment of Sorghum Landraces in Zimbabwe Using Microsatellites and Indigenous Local Names. *International Journal of Botany*, 2: 29-35.

Chanza. N (2018). Limits to climate change adaptation in Zimbabwe: Insights, experiences and lessons. *Climate Change Management*. Springer, Cham. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-6459956

Chen. J, Chopra. R, Hayes. C, Morris. G, Marla. S, Burke. J, Xin. Z and Burow. G (2017). Genome-wide association study of developing leaves' heat tolerance during vegetative growth stages in a Sorghum Association Panel. *Plant Genome* 10(2):1–15

Chikuta. S, Odong. T, Kabi. F and Rubaihayo. P (2015). Phenotypic Diversity of Selected Dual-Purpose Forage and Grain Sorghum Genotypes. *American Journal of Experimental Agriculture* 9:1-9.

Chiluwal. A, Bheemanahalli. R, Perumal. R, Asebedo. AR, Bashi. E, Lamsal. A, Sebela. D, Shetty. N. J and Jagadish S. V. K (2018). Integrated aerial and destructive phenotyping differentiates chilling stress tolerance during early seedling growth in sorghum. *Field Crops Research* 227:1–10

Chopart. J. L, Sine. B, Dao. A and Muller. B (2008). Root orientation of four sorghum cultivars: application to estimate root length density from root counts in soil profiles. *Plant Root* 2: 67-75. doi:10.3117/plantroot.2.67

Comprehensive agricultural policy framework (2012-2032) executive summary April 2012.

Cowan. M. F, Blomstedt. C. K, Norton. S. L, Henry. R. J, Møller. B. L and Gleadow. R (2020). Crop wild relatives as a genetic resource for generating low-cyanide, drought-tolerant Sorghum. *Environmental Experimental Botany* 169:103884

Cruz. C. D, Carneiro. P. C. S, and Regazzi. A. J. (2014). *Modelos Biométricos Aplicados ao Melhoramento Genético*. Viçosa: Editora da UFV.

Dehghani. H, Sabaghnia. N and Moghaddam. M (2009). Interpretation of genotype-by-environment interaction for late maize hybrids' grain yield using a biplot method. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture* 33:139–148

Dereje. G, Adisu. T, Mengesha. M and Bogale. T (2016). The Influence of Intercropping Sorghum with Legumes for Management and Control of Striga in Sorghum at Assosa Zone, Benshangul Gumuz Region, Western Ethiopia, East Africa. *Advances in Crop Science and Technology* 4:1-5.

Djurovic. D, Madic. M, Bokan. N, Stevovic. V, Tomic. D and Tanaskovic S (2014). Stability parameters for grain yield and its component traits in maize hybrids of different FAO maturity groups. *Journal of Central European Agriculture* 15:199–212

Dossou-Aminon. I, Loko. L, Adjatin. A, Dansi. A, Elangovan. M, Chaudhary. P, Vodouhè. R and Sanni. A (2014). Diversity, genetic erosion and farmers' preference of sorghum varieties [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] in North-Eastern Benin. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 3:531-552.

Dossou-Aminon. I, Yéyinou. L. I, Arlette Adjatin. A and Eben-Ezer. B. K (2015). Genetic divergence in northern Benin sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench) landraces as revealed by

agromorphological traits and selection of candidate genotypes. Hindawi Publishing Corporation. The Scientific World Journal Volume 2015, Article ID 916476 *Econometrica* 3: 353 – 365

Dube. C (2008). The impact of Zimbabwe's drought policy on Sontala Rural Community in Matabeleland South Province. MSc Thesis, Department of geology, Geography and environmental studies; Stellenbosch University.

Duressa. D, Weerasoriya. D, Bean. S. R, Tilley. M and Tesso. T (2018). Genetic basis of protein digestibility in grain sorghum. *Crop Science* 58(6):2183–2199

Ejeta. G (2007). The Striga scourge in Africa: a growing pandemic, integrating new technologies for Striga control: towards ending the witch-hunt, World Scientific. pages. 3-16.

Elangovan. M, Jain. S. K. and Patel. N. V (2013). Characterisation of sorghum germplasm collected from Gujarat. *Indian Journal of Plant Genetic Resources* 26(1): 42-46.

Elkonin. L. A, Italianskaya. J. V, Fadeeva. I. Y, Bychkova. V. V and Kozhemyakin. V. V (2013). In vitro protein digestibility in grain sorghum: effect of genotype and interaction with starch digestibility. *Euphytica* 193(3):327–337

Ezeaku. I. E and Mohammed. S. G (2006). Character association and path analysis in grain sorghum. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 5 (14) : 1337-1340

Falconer. D. S. (1989). Introduction to quantitative genetic. New York: Longman Scientific and Technical.

Farshadfar, E, Mohammadi, R, Aghaee, M and Vaisi, Z (2012). GGE biplot analysis of genotype x environment interaction in wheat-barley disomic addition lines. *Australian Journal of Crop Science* 6(6):1074-1079.

Fenty, J. 2004. Analysing distances. *The Strata Journal* 4: 1- 26

Fisher, R. A (1935). The mathematical distributions used in the common tests of significance.

Food and agriculture organization FAO. (2010). Crop and Livestock Assessment. Second round. (Unpublished Document.)

Gauch H.G., Piepho H.P., Annicchiarico P., (2008): Statistical Analysis of Yield Trials by AMMI and GGE: Further Considerations. *Crop Science* 48: 866-889.

Gauch, H. G (2006). Statistical analysis of yield trials by AMMI and GGE. *Crop Science* 46:1488-1500.

Geleta, N, Labuschagne, M and Viljoen, C. D (2006). Genetic diversity analysis in sorghum germplasm as estimated by AFLP, SSR and morpho-agronomical markers. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 15(10):3251-3265 DOI:10.1007/s10531-005-0313-7

Gerrano, A. S, Jansen van Rensburg, W. S, Mathew, I, Shayanowako, A. I. T, Bairu, M. W, Venter, S. L, Swart, W, Mofokeng, A, Mellem, J and Labuschagne, M (2020). Genotype and genotype x environment interaction effects on the grain yield performance of cowpea genotypes in dryland farming system in South Africa. *Euphytica* (2020) 216:80 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-020-02611-z>

Gill. P. K, Sharma. A. D, Singh. P and Bhullar. S. S (2001). Effect of various abiotic stresses on the growth, soluble sugars and water relations of sorghum seedlings grown in light and darkness. *Bulgary Journal of Plant Physiology* 27:72-84.

Gill. P. K., Sharma. A. D, Singh. P and Bhullar. S. S (2003). Changes in germination, growth and soluble sugar contents of *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench seeds under various abiotic stresses. *Plant growth regulation* 40:157-162.

Hadebe. S. T, Modi. A. T and Mabhaudi. T (2016). Drought Tolerance and Water Use of Cereal Crops: A Focus on Sorghum as a Food Security Crop in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science* 230 (3): 177-191.

Harlan. J. R and De Wet .J. M. J (1972). A simplified classification of cultivated sorghum. *Crop Science* 12:127-176.

Huntington. J. L, Hegewisch K. C, Daudert B, Morton C. G, Abatzoglou J. T, McEvoy. D. J and Erickson. T (2017). Climate engine: Cloud computing and visualization of climate and remote sensing data for advanced natural resource monitoring and process understanding. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 98: 2397–2409.

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2007). Climate change: synthesis report. Contributions of working groups I, II and III to the fourth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change. IPCC, Geneva.

Iqbal. A, Sadia.B, Khan.A.I, Awan.F.S, Kainth.R. A, Sadaqat.H.A (2010). Biodiversity in the sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench) germplasm of Pakistan. *Genetics and Molecular Research*. 9 (2) 756-764.

IRRI (2013). Plant Breeding Tools (PBTools) Version 1.3: International Rice Research Institute. Los Baños, the Philippines.

IRRI (2013). Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research (STAR) version 2.01: International Rice Research Institute. Los Baños, the Philippines

Jolliffe. I. T and Cadima. J (2016). Principal component analysis: a review and recent developments. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A* 374: 20150202.

Jordan. D. R, Mace. E. S, Henzell. R. G, Klein. P. E and Klein. R. R (2010). Molecular mapping and candidate gene identification of the Rf2 gene for pollen fertility restoration in sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench]. *Theory and Applied Genetic* 120:1279–1287

Kamuntu. S. P (2010). Phenotypic and genetic diversity of sweet sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) varieties and their suitability for ethanol production in Tanzania. Msc. Thesis. Sokoine University of Agriculture, Tanzania.

Kanbar A, Shakeri E, Alhajturki D, Horn T, Emam Y, Tabatabaei SA, Nick P(2019). Morphological and molecular characterization of sweet, grain and forage sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) genotypes grown under temperate climatic conditions, *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with all Aspects of Plant Biology*.doi: 10.1080/11263504.2019.1569568.

Kang, M. Genotype-Environment Interaction and Stability Analyses: An Update. In *Quantitative Genetics, Genomics and Plant Breeding*; Kansas State University: Manhattan, KS, USA, 2020.

Karadi. A and Kajjidoni. S. T (2020). Principal component analysis for productivity and grain quality traits in rabi sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench). *International Journal of Chemical Studies* 8(5): 2206-2216. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22271/chemi.2020.v8.i5ad.10636>.

Kaufman. R. C, Wilson. J. D, Bean. S. R, Galant. A. L, Perumal. R. R, Tesso. T, Herald. T and Shi Y. C (2018). Influence of genotype× location interaction on grain sorghum grain chemistry and digestibility. *Agronomy Journal* 110(5):1681–1688

Khandelwal. V, Shukla. M, Jodha. B. Nathawat. V. S and Dashora. S. K (2015). Genetic Parameters and Character Association in Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench). *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 8(22), 73902

Khizzah BW, Miller FR, Newton RJ (1993) Inheritance and heritability of heat tolerance in several sorghum cultivars during the reproductive phase. *African Crop Science Journal* 1(2)

Krupa. K. N, Dalawai. N, Shashidhar. H. E, Harinikumar. K. M, Manojkumar. H. B, Bharani. S and Turaida. V (2017). Mechanisms of Drought Tolerance in Sorghum: A Review, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Bioscience* 5(4): 221-237 doi:10.18782/2320-7051.2845.

Lenka. S, Lenka. N. K, Sejian. V and Mohanty. M (2015). Contribution of Agriculture Sector to Climate Change. *Climate Change Impact on Livestock: Adaptation and Mitigation*, DOI 10.1007/978-81-322-2265-1_3, © Springer.

Lin. C. S. and Binns. M. R (1988). A superiority measure of cultivar performance for cultivar× location data. *Canadian Journal of Plant Science* 68:193-198

Liu. G, Campbell. B. C and Godwin. I. D (2014). Sorghum genetic transformation by particle bombardment. *Cereal genomics*. Humana Press, Totowa, 219–234

Lombardi. G. M. R, Nunes. J. A. R, Parrella. R. A. C, Teixeira D. H. L, Bruzi. A. T, Durães. N. N. L, Fagundes. T. G (2015). Path analysis of agro-industrial traits in sweet sorghum. *Genetic Molecular Research* 14:16392–16402.

Ludlow. M. M and Muchow. R. C (1990). A critical evaluation of traits for improving crop yield in water-limited environments. *Advanced Agronomy* 43: 107-153.

Machado. N. G, Lotufo-Neto. N and Hongyu. K (2019). Statistical analysis for genotype stability and adaptability in maize yield based on environment and genotype interaction models. Federal University of Santa Maria. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5902/2179460X32873>.

Mangena. P, Shimelis. H, Laing. M (2018). Characterisation of sweet stem sorghum genotypes for bio-ethanol production. *Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica, Section B. Soil and Plant Science*, 68(4): 323-333, DOI: 10.1080/09064710.2017.1400586

Marla. S. R, Burow. G, Chopra. R, Hayes. C, Olatoye. M. O, Felderhof. T, Hu. Z, Raymundo. R, Perumal. R and Morris. G. P (2019). Genetic architecture of chilling tolerance in sorghum dissected with a nested association mapping population. *G3 Genes Genomes Genetics* 9(12):4045–4057

Masson-Delmotte. V, Zhai. P, Pörtner. H. O, Roberts. D, Skea. J, Shukla. P. R, Pirani. A, Moufouma-Okia. W, Péan. C, Pidcock. R, Connors. S, Matthews. J. B. R, Chen. Y, Zhou. X, Gomis. M. I, Lonnoy. E, Maycock. T, Tignor. M, Waterfeld. T (2019). Global warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC special report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty. IPCC, Geneva

Matthew. S (2015). The feasibility of small grains as an adoptive strategy to climate change. Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio- Economic Sciences, 4(15): 40–55

Mendiburu F de. (2020). agricolae: Statistical procedures for agricultural research. R package version 1.3-3. Available from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/agricolae/index.html>
Accessed 5 December 2021

Menz. M. A, Klein. R. R., Unruh. N. C, Rooney W. L, Klein P .E and Mullet. J. E (2004). Genetic diversity of public inbreds of sorghum determined by mapped AFLP and SSR markers. Crop science 44:1236-1244.

Mitrovia. B, Treski. S, Stojakovia. M, Ivanovia. M and Bekavac. G (2012). Evaluation of experimental maize hybrids tested in multi-location trials using AMMI and GGE biplot analyses. Turkish Journal of Field Crops 17(1):35–40

Mofokeng. A. M, Shimelis. H and Laing. M (2017). Breeding strategies to improve sorghum quality. Australian journal of crop science. 11(2):142-148. doi: 10.21475/ajcs.17.11.02.p127

Mohamed. N. E. M (2013). Genotype by environment interactions for grain yield in bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). Journal of Plant Breeding and Crop Science, 5: 150-157.

Mohammed. R, Are1. A. K, Bhavanasi. R, Munghate. R. S, Kishor. P. B. K and Sharma. H. C (2015). Quantitative genetic analysis of agronomic and morphological traits in sorghum, *Sorghum bicolor*. Frontiers in Plant Science 6:945. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2015.00945

Mohan. S and Thiyagarajan. K. (2019). Genetic Variability, Correlation and Path Coefficient Analysis in Chickpea (*Cicer Arietinum* L.) for Yield and its Component Traits. International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences, Volume 8 (ISSN: 2319-7706).

Mousavi-Derazmahalleh. M, Bayer. P. E, Hane. J. K, Babu. V, Nguyen. H. T, Nelson. M. N, Erskine. W, Varshney. R. K, Papa. R and Edwards D (2018). Adapting legume crops to climate change using genomic approaches. *Plant Cell Environment* 42:6–19

Mujaju. C and Chakauya. E (2008). Morphological Variation of Sorghum Landrace Accessions On-Farm in Semi-Arid Areas of Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Botany*, 4: 376-382

Mulima. E. P (2017). Genetic diversity of sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench) germplasm and hybrid potential under contrasting environments in Mozambique. A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Plant Breeding. University of KwaZulu-Natal.

Mungra. K, Jadhav. B. and Khandelwal. V (2011). Genetic analysis for yield and quality traits in forage sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench]. *The Indian Journal of Genetics and Plant Breeding* 71:223-230.

Murtagh. F and Heck. A (2012). *Multivariate data analysis* Springer Science and Business Media, Queen's University Belfast, and Astronomical Observatory Strasbourg

Muzerengi. T and Tirivangasi. H. M (2019). Small grain production as an adaptive strategy to climate change in Mangwe District, Matabeleland South in Zimbabwe. *Jamba: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies* 11(1):1-9. DOI:10.4102/jamba.v11i1.652.

Nagaraju. M, Sudhakar. Reddy. P, Anil Kumar. S, Srivastava. R. K, Kavi Kishor. P. B and Rao. D. M (2015). Genome-wide scanning and characterization of *Sorghum bicolor* L. heat shock transcription factors. *Current Genomics* 16(4):279–291

Nciizah. T, Nciizah. E, Mubekaphi. C and Nciizah. A. D (2021). Role of Small Grains in Adapting to Climate Change: Zvishavane District, Zimbabwe. African Handbook of Climate Change Adaptation. Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-45106-6_254.

Ndlovu. E , Van Staden. J and Maphosa. M (2021). Morpho-physiological effects of moisture, heat and combined stresses on Sorghum bicolor [Moench (L.)] and its acclimation mechanisms. Plant Stress. Doi.org/10.1016/j.stress.2021.100018

Neisse. A. C, Kirch. J. L and Hongyu. K (2018). AMMI and GGE Biplot for genotype × environment interaction: a medoid-based hierarchical cluster analysis approach for high dimensional data. Biometrical Letters 55 (2): 97-121. DOI: 10.2478/bile-2018-0008

Nelson. G. C, Rosegrant. M. W, Koo. J, Robertson. R, Sulser. T, Zhu. T, Ringler. C, Msangi. S, Palazzo. A, Batka. M, Magalhaes. M, Valmonte-Santos. R, Ewing. M and Lee. D (2009). Climate Change: Impact on Agriculture and Costs of Adaptation. Food Policy Report. International Food Policy Research Institute. DOI: 10.2499/0896295354.

Olembo. K. N, M'Mboyi. F and Kiplagat. S (2010). Sorghum breeding in Sub-Saharan Africa. African Journal of Biotechnology:40-40.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2016). Agriculture and Climate Change: Towards Sustainable, Productive and Climate-Friendly Agricultural Systems. Background note 4.

Pabendon. M B, Fendi.R.E, Santoso .S. B and Prastowo.B (2017). Varieties of sweet sorghum Super-1 and Super-2 and its equipment for bioethanol in Indonesia. International Conference on Biomass: Technology, Application, and Sustainable Development.

Payne. R. W, Harding. S. A, Murray. D. A, Soutar. D. M, Baird. D. B, Glaser. A. I, Channing. I. C, Welham. S. J, Gilmour. A. R, Thompson. R and Webster. R (2010). The Guide to GenStat Release 13, Part 2: Statistics. VSN International, Hemel Hempstead, UK

Phiri. K, Dube. T, Moyo. P, Ncube. C and Ndlovu. S (2019). Small grains “resistance”? Making sense of Zimbabwean smallholder farmers’ cropping choices and patterns within a climate change context. *Cogent Social Sciences* 5 (1)

Popat. R, Patel. R and Parmar. D (2020). Variability: Genetic Variability Analysis for Plant Breeding Research. Available at <https://cran.r-project.org/package=variability>. Accessed: 7 December 2021.

Popović. V, Ljubičić. N, Kostić. M, Radulović. M, Blagojević. D, Ugrenović. V, Popović. D and Ivošević. B (2020) Genotype × Environment Interaction for Wheat Yield Traits Suitable for Selection in Different Seed Priming Conditions. *Plants* 2020, 9, 1804

Ramatoulaye F, Mady C, Fallou S, Amadou K, Cyril D and Massamba D (2016). Production and Use Sorghum: A Literature Review. *Journal of Nutritional Health & Food Science* 4(1): 1-4.

Rao. A. S, Rao. P. K. E, Mengesha. M. H and Reddy. G. V (1999). Morphological diversity in sorghum germplasm from India. *Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution*, 43 : 559-567.

Ravikesavan, R. (2006). Genetic diversity in cotton (*Gossypium* sp) (pp. 11-13). National conference on plant sciences research and development. APSI scientist meet, PSG CAS, Coimbatore, India.

Raza. A, Razzaq. A, Mehmood. S. S, Zou. X, Zhang. X, Liv. Y and Xu. J (2019). Impact of climate change on crops adaptation and strategies to tackle its outcome: a review. *Plants* 8(2):34

- Reddy. B. V. S, Sharma. H. C, Thakur. R. P, Ramesh. S and Ashok Kumar. A (2007). Characterization of ICRISAT bred sorghum hybrid parents (Set II). *International Sorghum and Millets Newsletter* 48:1–123
- Rhodes. D. H, Hofmann. L, Rooney. W. L, Herald. T. J, Bean. S, Boyles. R, Brenton. Z. W and Kresovich. S (2017). Genetic architecture of kernel composition in global sorghum germplasm. *BMC Genomics* 18(1):1–8
- Riaz. A, Li. G, Quresh. Z, Swati. M. S and Quiros. C .F (2003). Genetic diversity of oilseed *Brassica napus* inbred lines based on sequence-related amplified polymorphism and its relation to hybrid performance. *Plant Breeding* 120: 411-415.
- Seetharam. K and Ganesamurthy. K. (2013). Research Note Characterization of sorghum genotypes for yield and other agronomic traits through genetic variability and diversity analysis. *Electronic Journal of Plant Breeding* 4:1073-1079
- Shewale. S and Aniruddha. P (2011). Uses of sorghum and value addition. *Sorghum cultivation, varieties and uses* 1-44.
- Shukla. S, Bhargava. A and Chatterjee. A (2006). Genotypic variability in vegetable amaranth (*Amaranthus tricolor* L for foliage yield and its contributing traits over successive cuttings and years. *Euphytica* 151: 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-006-9134-3>
- Silva. D.D, Costa. R.V, Cota. L.V, Figueiredo. J.E, Casela. C.R and Lanza. F.E (2015). Genotype rotation for leaf anthracnose disease management in sorghum. *Crop Protection* 67:145-150.
- Singh R. K and Chaudhary. B. D (1979). *Biometrical methods in quantitative genetic analysis*. Kalyani publication, New Delhi :120.

- Sinha. S and Kumaravadivel. N (2016). Understanding Genetic Diversity of Sorghum Using Quantitative Traits. Hindawi Publishing Corporation Scientifica. Doi 10.1155/2016/3075023
- Svodziwa. M (2015). The feasibility of small grains as an adoptive strategy to climate change. Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences. 5: 41
- T. Shehzad, H. Okuizumi, M. Kawase, and K. Okuno (2009). “Development of SSR based sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) diversity research set of germplasm and its evaluation by morphological traits,” Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution 56 (6): 809–827.
- Taremwa. N. K, Gashumba. D, Butera. A and Ranganathan. T (2016). Climate change adaptation in Rwanda through Indigenous knowledge practice. Journal of Social Sciences, 46(2), 165–175. doi:10.1080/09718923.2016.11893524
- Tariq. A. S, Akram. Z, Shabbir. G, Gulfraz. M, Khan. K. S, Iqbal. M. S, and Mahmood. T (2012). Character association and inheritance studies of different sorghum genotypes for fodder yield and quality under irrigated and rain fed conditions. African Journal of Biotechnology.11(38): 9189-9195. DOI: 10.5897/AJB11.2561
- Tesfaye. K (2017). Genetic diversity study of sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) genotypes, Ethiopia. Acta universitatis sapientiae agriculture and environment, 9: 44-54
- Tesso. T, Ejeta. G, Chandrashekar. A, Huang. C. P, Tandjung A, Lewamy. M, Axtell. J. D and Hamaker. B. R (2006). A novel modified endosperm texture in a mutant high-protein digestibility/high-lysine grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench). Cereal Chemistry Journal 83:194–201

Tuinstra. M. R, Grote. E. M, Goldbrough. P. M and Ejeta. G (1997). Genetic analysis of post flowering drought tolerance and components of grain development in *Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench. *Molecular Breeding* 3:439–448

Turner. D. L. The use of specialty sorghums for expanded snack food processing. Master's Thesis.

Verma. R, Kumar. R and Nath. A (2018). Drought Resistance Mechanism and Adaptation to Water Stress in Sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench]. *International Journal of Bio-resource and Stress Management* 9(1):167-172.

Verma. R, Ranwah B. R, Bharti. B, Kumar. R, Kunwar. R, Diwaker. A and Meena. M (2017). Characterization of Sorghum germplasm for various qualitative traits. *Journal of Applied and Natural Science* 9 (2): 1002 – 1007.

Vieira. E. A, Carvalho. F. I .F, Bertran. I, Kopp. M. M, Zimmer. P. D, Benin. G, Silva. J. A, Hartwig. I, Malone. G and Oliveira. A. C (2007). Association between genetic distance in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) as estimated by AFLP and morphological markers. *Genetic and Molecular Biology* 30: 392-399.

Waddington. S. R, Li. X, Dixon. J, Hyman. G. and De Vicente. M.C. (2010). Getting the focus right: production constraints for six major food crops in Asian and African farming systems. *Food security* 2:27-48.

Walle. T, Mekbib. F, Amsalu. B and Gedil. M (2018). Correlation and Path Coefficient Analyses of Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L.) Landraces in Ethiopia. *American Journal of Plant Sciences*, 9, 2794–2812. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajps.2018.913202>

- Warburton. M, Reif. J, Frisch. M, Bohn. M, Bedoya. C, Xia. X, Crossa. J, Franco. J, Hoisington. D and Pixley. K (2008). Genetic diversity in CIMMYT nontemperate maize germplasm: landraces, open pollinated varieties, and inbred lines. *Crop Science* 48:617-624.
- Wasihun. L (2007). Agro-morphological characterization of Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L) Moench Landraces from Metekel area, MSc Thesis. Hawasa University, Ethiopia. 104pp.
- White. J. A, Ryley. M. J., George. D. L, Kong. G. A. and White S. C (2012). Yield losses in grain sorghum due to rust infection. *Australasian Plant Pathology* 41:85-91
- Wong. J. H, Marx. D. B, Wilson. J. D, Buchanan. B. B, Lemaux. P. G and Pedersen. J. F (2010). Principal component analysis and biochemical characterization of protein and starch reveal primary targets for improving sorghum grain. *Plant Science* 179(6):598–611
- Wuhaib. K. M, Hadi. B. H and Hassan. W. A (2017). Genetic Parameters for Sorghum Varieties in Different Population Densities. *International Journal of Applied Agricultural Sciences* 3(1): 19-24. Doi: 10.11648/j.ijaas.20170301.12
- Xiong. L, Wang. R, Mao. G and Koezan. J (2006). Identification of drought tolerance determinants by genetic analysis of root responses to drought stress and abscisic acid. *Plant Physiology* 142: 1065-1074.
- Yan. W and Kang M.S (2003). In: “GGE-biplot Analysis: A graphical Tool for Breeders”. Genet and Agronomists, CRD Press, Boca Raton
- Yan. W and Rajcan. I (2002). Biplot analysis of test sites and trait relations of soybean in Ontario. *Crop Science* 42(1):11–20

Yan. W and Tinker. N. A (2006) .Biplot analysis of multi-environment trial data: principles and applications. Canadian Journal of Plant Sciences 86(3):623–645

Yan. W and Tinker. N. A (2006). Biplot analysis of multi-environmental trial data: Principles and applications. Canadian Journal of Plant Science 1:623-645.

Yan. W, Kang. M. S, Ma. B, Woods. S and Cornelius. P. L (2007). GGE biplot vs. AMMI analysis of genotype-by-environment data. Crop Science 47:643-653.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1 : ANOVA table for AMMI model

Source	df	SS	MS	F	F_prob
Total	293	660313434	2253629	*	*
Treatments	146	501882829	3437554	3.22	0.00000
Genotypes	48	253161125	5274190	4.94	0.00000
Environments	2	132766048	66383024	43.10	0.00000
Block	3	4620311	1540104	1.44	0.23310
Interactions	96	115955656	1207871	1.13	0.25035
IPCA	49	72171547	1472889	1.38	0.07454
IPCA	47	43784109	931577	0.87	0.70090
Residuals	0	0	*	*	*
Error	144	153810294	1068127	*	*

NB: the block source of variation refers to blocks within environments

Appendix 2: Environment means and scores

Environment	NE	Em	IPCAe[1]	IPCAe[2]
E1	1	3202	-63.16510	-3.41035
E2	2	1558	28.23604	49.98275
E3	3	2314	34.92906	-46.57240

Appendix 3: Environment means and variances

	Nobserved	Mean	Variance
Env			
1	98	3202	2756605
2	98	1558	785191
3	98	2314	1896837
Margin	294	2358	2253629

Appendix 4: AMMI-estimates per environment

Environment	1	AMMI-estimates	Ranked
GB 102	3763	GB 92	6352
GB 123	4258	ICR 123	6255
GB 124	3702	SV 2	6214
GB 13	3202	GB 61	5350
GB 134	4848	GB 43	5060
GB 136	4470	GB 134	4848
GB 137	2663	GB 2	4594
GB 144	2967	GB 56	4501
GB 15	2657	GB 136	4470
GB 172	2782	GB 123	4258
GB 175	2955	ICR 20	4232
GB 185	4140	GB 185	4140
GB 19	1794	ICR 116	3970
GB 2	4594	ICR 19	3922
GB 30	2413	GB 102	3763
GB 43	5060	GB 124	3702
GB 56	4501	ICR 61	3667
GB 61	5350	ICR 17	3621
GB 82	3278	ICR 28	3548
GB 88	1941	ICR 14	3515
GB 92	6352	ICR 142	3417
GB 94	2838	ICR 16	3302
GB 98	3042	ICR 65	3289
ICR 1	787	GB 82	3278
ICR 116	3970	GB 13	3202
ICR 123	6255	ICR 21	3075
ICR 14	3515	GB 98	3042
ICR 142	3417	GB 144	2967
ICR 154	607	GB 175	2955
ICR 16	3302	Macia	2952
ICR 17	3621	SV 4	2944
ICR 19	3922	GB 94	2838
ICR 20	4232	GB 172	2782
ICR 21	3075	GB 137	2663
ICR 28	3548	GB 15	2657
ICR 34	2448	ICR 40	2451
ICR 40	2451	ICR 34	2448
ICR 5	2014	GB 30	2413
ICR 52	1173	ICR 5	2014
ICR 54	1417	GB 88	1941
ICR 6	419	GB 19	1794
ICR 61	3667	ICR 7	1624

ICR 65	3289	ICR 8	1573
ICR 7	1624	ICR 54	1417
ICR 74	887	ICR 52	1173
ICR 8	1573	ICR 74	887
Macia	2952	ICR 1	787
SV 2	6214	ICR 154	607
SV 4	2944	ICR 6	419

Environment	2	AMMI-estimates	Ranked
GB 102	1652	ICR 61	3320
GB 123	2423	Macia	2966
GB 124	1928	GB 175	2728
GB 13	2031	ICR 40	2632
GB 134	1609	GB 2	2559
GB 136	2164	SV 4	2429
GB 137	1322	GB 30	2427
GB 144	1511	GB 123	2423
GB 15	1063	ICR 116	2268
GB 172	1581	GB 92	2197
GB 175	2728	GB 136	2164
GB 185	1591	ICR 20	2142
GB 19	2042	GB 19	2042
GB 2	2559	ICR 123	2034
GB 30	2427	GB 13	2031
GB 43	1848	SV 2	1991
GB 56	1971	GB 56	1971
GB 61	1648	GB 124	1928
GB 82	1860	GB 82	1860
GB 88	857	GB 43	1848
GB 92	2197	GB 94	1672
GB 94	1672	GB 102	1652
GB 98	1240	GB 61	1648
ICR 1	132	ICR 21	1645
ICR 116	2268	GB 134	1609
ICR 123	2034	GB 185	1591
ICR 14	837	GB 172	1581
ICR 142	1278	ICR 34	1521
ICR 154	84	GB 144	1511
ICR 16	1196	ICR 28	1345
ICR 17	1119	GB 137	1322
ICR 19	1121	ICR 142	1278
ICR 20	2142	GB 98	1240
ICR 21	1645	ICR 16	1196
ICR 28	1345	ICR 19	1121
ICR 34	1521	ICR 17	1119

ICR 40	2632	GB 15	1063
ICR 5	941	ICR 65	1027
ICR 52	94	ICR 5	941
ICR 54	259	GB 88	857
ICR 6	730	ICR 14	837
ICR 61	3320	ICR 6	730
ICR 65	1027	ICR 7	600
ICR 7	600	ICR 8	396
ICR 74	286	ICR 74	286
ICR 8	396	ICR 54	259
Macia	2966	ICR 1	132
SV 2	1991	ICR 52	94
SV 4	2429	ICR 154	84

Environment	3	AMMI-estimates	Ranked
GB 102	1188	ICR 19	4588
GB 123	3515	SV 2	4510
GB 124	1088	SV 4	4139
GB 13	2015	GB 98	4071
GB 134	2321	GB 92	3965
GB 136	3881	GB 136	3881
GB 137	2883	Macia	3616
GB 144	1437	ICR 142	3562
GB 15	1408	GB 123	3515
GB 172	2820	GB 19	3281
GB 175	2463	ICR 116	3017
GB 185	2744	ICR 61	3013
GB 19	3281	GB 2	3007
GB 2	3007	GB 137	2883
GB 30	2416	GB 172	2820
GB 43	2775	GB 43	2775
GB 56	2212	ICR 5	2754
GB 61	2040	GB 185	2744
GB 82	1823	ICR 123	2689
GB 88	1249	ICR 20	2536
GB 92	3965	GB 175	2463
GB 94	1912	ICR 7	2429
GB 98	4071	GB 30	2416
ICR 1	588	ICR 17	2350
ICR 116	3017	ICR 14	2325
ICR 123	2689	GB 134	2321
ICR 14	2325	ICR 65	2311
ICR 142	3562	ICR 16	2221
ICR 154	105	GB 56	2212
ICR 16	2221	ICR 34	2101

ICR 17	2350	GB 61	2040
ICR 19	4588	GB 13	2015
ICR 20	2536	GB 94	1912
ICR 21	1218	GB 82	1823
ICR 28	1123	GB 144	1437
ICR 34	2101	ICR 40	1420
ICR 40	1420	GB 15	1408
ICR 5	2754	ICR 74	1407
ICR 52	462	ICR 8	1402
ICR 54	895	GB 88	1249
ICR 6	83	ICR 21	1218
ICR 61	3013	GB 102	1188
ICR 65	2311	ICR 28	1123
ICR 7	2429	GB 124	1088
ICR 74	1407	ICR 54	895
ICR 8	1402	ICR 1	588
Macia	3616	ICR 52	462
SV 2	4510	ICR 154	105
SV 4	4139	ICR 6	83

Appendix 5: Table of first four AMMI selections per environment

Number	Environment	Mean	Score	1	2	3	4
3	E3	2314	34.93	ICR 19	SV 2	SV 4	GB 98
2	E2	1558	28.24	ICR 61	Macia	GB 175	ICR 40
1	E1	3202	-63.17	GB 92	ICR 123	SV 2	GB 61

Appendix 6: Agglomerative cluster analysis tables

Specifications:

Distance Method: Euclidean

Clustering Method: Ward

Number of Clusters: 4

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	StdDev
DMA	64.00	121.00	82.17	14.00
PH	115.00	300.00	242.04	48.94
PC	10.00	52.00	32.13	10.21
PT	0.00	2.00	0.37	0.55
nPT	0.00	2.00	0.38	0.58
NL	8.00	19.00	13.24	2.77
LL	56.00	98.00	78.98	8.42
LW	5.00	10.00	7.61	1.14
SD	11.50	25.18	18.88	3.27
EXTN	0.00	21.30	7.38	5.94
HS	13.50	33.00	23.53	4.61
HW	452.00	4100.00	2016.89	785.19
GYD	439.50	4480.00	2147.77	931.69

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Cluster	Min	Max	Mean	StdDev
DMA	1	81.00	121.00	100.79	13.14
DMA	2	64.00	82.00	74.54	5.45

DMA	3	67.50	84.00	73.96	5.30
DMA	4	67.00	102.00	80.04	9.85
PH	1	225.50	300.00	275.25	30.76
PH	2	115.00	300.00	240.46	55.74
PH	3	147.00	300.00	224.54	45.50
PH	4	151.50	300.00	228.04	47.89
PC	1	25.00	50.00	38.25	9.17
PC	2	17.00	47.00	32.69	9.28
PC	3	15.00	52.00	34.38	9.94
PC	4	10.00	34.00	23.17	6.63
PT	1	0.00	1.00	0.25	0.40
PT	2	0.00	1.00	0.19	0.38
PT	3	0.00	2.00	1.04	0.54
PT	4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
nPT	1	0.00	2.00	0.62	0.61
nPT	2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
nPT	3	0.00	2.00	0.92	0.63
nPT	4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
NL	1	14.50	19.00	16.92	1.47
NL	2	8.00	16.00	11.81	2.12
NL	3	9.00	13.00	11.17	1.05
NL	4	10.00	16.00	13.21	1.84
LL	1	71.50	98.00	87.46	6.58
LL	2	67.00	91.50	78.65	7.21
LL	3	56.00	80.50	71.54	6.72

LL	4	72.50	85.00	78.29	4.97
LW	1	6.00	9.00	7.54	0.99
LW	2	5.00	10.00	7.54	1.33
LW	3	5.00	9.00	7.17	1.05
LW	4	7.00	10.00	8.21	1.01
SD	1	18.84	25.18	21.66	2.17
SD	2	11.50	20.23	17.68	2.29
SD	3	12.97	19.06	15.51	1.88
SD	4	16.42	24.61	20.76	2.52
EXTN	1	0.00	5.00	2.23	1.85
EXTN	2	0.00	16.20	8.75	5.44
EXTN	3	8.50	21.30	13.57	4.07
EXTN	4	0.00	16.00	4.86	4.65
HS	1	13.50	30.50	22.17	6.01
HS	2	19.00	33.00	24.42	3.95
HS	3	20.00	31.00	26.33	3.89
HS	4	16.00	25.00	21.12	2.55
HW	1	452.00	2739.00	1753.92	762.92
HW	2	1780.00	4100.00	2689.15	720.38
HW	3	672.00	2895.50	2074.54	639.65
HW	4	746.00	2301.00	1493.92	470.58
GYD	1	439.50	2634.00	1745.12	788.09
GYD	2	1880.00	4480.00	3149.92	773.00
GYD	3	707.00	3102.00	2053.12	708.62
GYD	4	875.00	2480.00	1559.38	511.44

CLUSTER MEMBERSHIP SUMMARY

Member of Cluster 1

ICR 54 Macia ICR 61 ICR 5 SV 4 ICR 142 GB 56 ICR 34 ICR 40 GB 92 ICR 8 GB 94

Member of Cluster 2

ICR 123 GB 15 ICR 19 ICR 7 ICR 28 ICR 20 GB 98 GB 61 GB 136 ICR 1 GB 43 ICR 116 GB
2

Member of Cluster 3

ICR 74 GB 123 GB 172 SV 2 ICR 65 GB 30 ICR 6 GB 13 GB 102 ICR 16 GB 82 ICR 52

Member of Cluster 4

GB 175 ICR 21 ICR 14 GB 19 ICR 154 ICR 17 GB 137 GB 185 GB 134 GB 124 GB 144 GB
88

Number of members in each cluster

Cluster	Size
1	12
2	13
3	12
4	12

COPHENETIC CORRELATION COEFFICIENT = 0.435